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Quantifying the Accuracy of Diffusion Map for Dimensionality Reduction Using Neural Networks

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Abstract

The diffusion map has seen frequent use as a nonlinear dimensionality reduction technique, with applications in many different fields. One aspect however is often overlooked: How much of the information in the original data is conserved by the dimensionality reduction? When it is considered at all, authors usually turn to the eigenvalue spectrum of the diffusion map. This thesis makes the case that the spectrum is unsuitable for this purpose. A new framework for measuring the quality of a dimensionality reduction mapping is therefore proposed. Called the Neural Reconstruction Error, it can be applied to any dimensionality reduction method and enjoys an intuitive interpretation. It extends the concept of the reconstruction error to nonparametric methods by having a neural network learn an approximate inverse. Unlike rank-based quality metrics of dimensionality reduction methods, it can be interpreted quantitatively similarly to the familiar variance explained in PCA. Tests on artificial and real-life datasets indicate that the Neural Reconstruction Error is able to quantify the quality of diffusion maps, consistent with intuition and theoretical predictions. It can be used to identify the most important diffusion components. Possible applications for data exploration are also demonstrated.

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1 Introduction

In our digitized world, there is no shortage of data. Thanks to ever cheaper processing and storage capabilities, there are less and less restrictions as to the amount of data that is collected. This allows datasets not only to be very large in terms of the number of data points, but also to be *high-dimensional*. This means that a large number of different quantities are measured for any given observation. Data from all areas of science and life is high-dimensional, whether it be computer vision, biology, sociology or medicine. This wealth of data certainly brings with it a lot of potential. However, the high dimensionality also poses a number of challenges.

For one, despite all the advanced statistical tools that we have, a major way to gain insight from data remains visualization. A plot lets us grasp relationships between variables at a glance and provides a starting point for further analysis. Visualization is also vital for communicating our results. However, it becomes unfeasible to plot more than a handful of variables at the same time.

Another challenge is what is called the *curse of dimensionality* [1]: As a space becomes higher-dimensional, the density of data points decreases exponentially with the number of dimensions. For instance, a million data points sounds like it should be more than enough for most analyses, but a million data points spanning a 20-dimensional space are comparable to just two data points in a one-dimensional space!¹ This is of course fatal for any task such as interpolation, which requires that sample points are not too far apart. In order to maintain the same density, the size of the available data would have to grow exponentially with the number of dimensions; collecting those amounts of data is of course unfeasible in many situations.

Luckily, it appears that in reality, the variables in a high-dimensional dataset are rarely all independent. Consider for instance a dataset of 100×100 pixel grayscale images, which we might want to use to train an image classifier. Each image can be thought of as an element of a 10,000-dimensional vector space, with each pixel constituting one dimension. Clearly, however, the pixels are not distributed independently; otherwise, almost all images would look like static noise. Instead, all images of recognizable objects must lie on a much lower-dimensional subset of the entire space. This is an example of the *manifold hypothesis*. It states that, in many high-dimensional datasets, the data lie on or near a manifold with lower dimension [2].

This is what makes *dimensionality reduction* possible. Its task is to map the high-dimensional dataset into a lower-dimensional space, whilst retaining the relevant features

¹In the sense that, in order to sample each corner of a 20-dimensional hypercube, we would require $2^{20} \approx 1,000,000$ data points. By contrast, the one-dimensional hypercube (line segment) only has two corners to be sampled.

of the dataset. Ideally the embedding space would have the same dimensionality as the data manifold. In many contexts, however, some amount of information loss is inevitable and acceptable. What features need to be retained depends on the application at hand. Dimensionality reduction can be used for many different purposes, including data visualization, compression, or as a preprocessing step to other methods, such as clustering and supervised learning [3].

By far the most widespread dimensionality reduction method is Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [4]. It consists in projecting the data onto a linear subspace which captures a maximum of the variance of the entire dataset. As a linear dimensionality reduction technique, it is easy to use, computationally efficient and requires no parameter choices. However, the linearity can be limiting. If the data manifold is highly nonlinear, PCA is unable to uncover it, leading to suboptimal or downright useless embeddings.

For this reason, a whole host of nonlinear dimensionality reduction techniques have been developed [5]. They can be categorized into several classes according to the approach that is used [3, 6]. For instance, t-SNE [7] is an example of a probabilistic method and autoencoders [8] are neural network based. What is probably the largest group, however, are the spectral methods. These include Kernel PCA [9], Laplacian eigenmap [10], Isomap [11], Locally Linear Embedding [12] and diffusion map [13]. They are all based on the eigendecomposition of a graph Laplacian or similar matrix, which encodes local neighborhood relations of the dataset. Many of these methods are closely related to each other. In fact, it has been shown that most spectral methods can be expressed as special cases of Kernel PCA [14].

This thesis focuses on one of the spectral dimensionality reduction methods, the *diffusion map*. It is distinguished by offering a probabilistic interpretation, giving it its name [15]. After its introduction in the 2000s, it has been used to study many subjects, such as the collective dynamics of animal groups [16] or pedestrians [17], molecular dynamics [18], cell differentiation [19] and the dynamics of domain walls [20]. Beyond the natural sciences, it has also found applications in studying, e.g., census data [21] or the evolution of democracies [22].

When applying the diffusion map in practice, a number of aspects need to be considered. This concerns the preprocessing of data and, importantly, finding suitable parameters for the diffusion map. And while there is some literature on finding an appropriate value for the important kernel width ϵ [23–27], a different question has not been answered satisfactorily. In diffusion map, like most other dimensionality reduction methods, one needs to decide the dimensionality of the lower-dimensional representation. In some other methods like PCA, this choice can be guided by a useful measure: The eigenvalues of the PCA indicate how much of the variance in the dataset is explained when using a given number of principal components. It is often claimed that for the diffusion map, the spectrum that results from the eigendecomposition can be used in a similar way [13, 15, 25]. However, as will be argued in this thesis, it can be misleading and is not suitable for this purpose. This leaves a gap where there is little useful guidance as to how many dimensions are needed in diffusion space to represent a dataset to some level of accuracy.

To address this problem, I propose in this thesis a framework, called *Neural Reconstruction Error*, to evaluate the quality of a diffusion map embedding. It is based on the reconstruction of the original data from the diffusion map by a neural network. We will see the versatile ways in which this method can be used, not only to decide on the number of diffusion components, but also to gain insight into a dataset. As it turns out, the Neural Reconstruction Error can be applied to any dimensionality reduction method, enabling quantitative comparisons across different methods.

This thesis is structured as follows: In chapter 2, the necessary prerequisites are covered. This includes an introduction to the diffusion map and, briefly, some elements of supervised learning that will be needed. Chapter 3 then focuses on the main topic of this thesis: How can the quality of a diffusion map embedding be quantified? After summarizing the existing approaches, the Neural Reconstruction Error is introduced in section 3.3. This represents the main contribution of this thesis. To my knowledge, it has not been used so far to evaluate the quality of diffusion map embeddings, although related approaches are also discussed. The rest of chapter 3 is dedicated to illustrating various aspects of the Neural Reconstruction Error on the example of the Swiss roll dataset. In chapter 4, the Neural Reconstruction Error is applied to three real-life datasets, confirming the validity of the method and demonstrating some use cases. The summary and discussion follow in chapter 5.

2 Background

2.1 Diffusion Map

The diffusion map as it is known today was first introduced by Coifman and Lafon [13]. This section summarizes its working principles and some of its properties. A good introduction to the diffusion map that focuses on their probabilistic interpretation has also been written by Nadler et al. [15], on which many of the following remarks are based.

Consider a dataset that consists of N observations of p features. We denote it $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^N$, with each $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$. We assume that the data points lie close to a manifold whose dimensionality is less than p . The goal of nonlinear dimensionality reduction in general, and diffusion map in particular, is now to parametrize that manifold. The diffusion map achieves this by first constructing a neighborhood graph on the data points. To that end, we construct a weight matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$:

$$W_{ij} = k(x_i, x_j), \quad (2.1)$$

where k is a suitable kernel function. The purpose of the kernel function is to introduce a nonlinearity in such a way that relationships between neighboring points are emphasized. This is because the points are expected to lie close to a possibly nonlinear manifold, which resembles a Euclidean space only locally, but not globally. Pairwise distances should therefore be preserved in a local neighborhood, but not necessarily globally. The most common choice of kernel function is the Gaussian kernel

$$k(x, y) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - y\|^2}{\epsilon}\right). \quad (2.2)$$

Here, ϵ is the parameter of the method, which we shall refer to as the kernel width for simplicity. Note that technically, however, the width of the Gaussian bump would be $\sqrt{2\epsilon}$. Other conventions are also in use, where the denominator in the exponent is denoted, e.g., ϵ^2 , $2\epsilon^2$, or 4ϵ [3, 15, 23, 28].

At this point, it is not uncommon to set all entries to zero, except for the K nearest neighbors of each point. That is, one can replace W with a matrix W' where

$$W'_{ij} = \begin{cases} W_{ij}, & \text{if } x_i \text{ is in the } K \text{ nearest neighbors of } x_j \text{ or vice-versa} \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

Alternatively, we can also set all entries to zero which lie under a certain threshold. In both cases, the goal is the same: to obtain a sparse matrix so that the following eigenvalue problem would be computationally less involved.

The next step has been introduced by Coifman and Lafon [13] under the name “anisotropic kernel” and is not always considered in the literature for the diffusion map. It consists in defining the matrix

$$W^{(\alpha)} = \tilde{D}^{-\alpha} W \tilde{D}^{-\alpha}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is a parameter and \tilde{D} is a diagonal matrix of normalization factors

$$\tilde{D}_{ii} = \sum_{j=1}^N W_{ij} \quad (2.5)$$

As we can see, choosing $\alpha = 0$ amounts to leaving out this step and setting $W^{(\alpha)} = W$. In section 2.1.2, it will become clear why including this step can make sense and what the meaning of α is.

Next, we define a random walk on the dataset by normalizing $W^{(\alpha)}$:

$$M = D^{-1} W^{(\alpha)}, \quad (2.6)$$

where D , just like above, is a diagonal matrix of normalization factors, but now for $W^{(\alpha)}$:

$$D_{ii} = \sum_{j=1}^N W_{ij}^{(\alpha)}. \quad (2.7)$$

M is a row stochastic matrix, with M_{ij} representing the probability of the random walk to jump from data point i to point j in one time step. Crucially, the random walk only ever moves along the data manifold, taking small steps each time. At least if ϵ is chosen appropriately, there are no large jumps spanning different regions of the manifold. M can therefore be thought of as defining a diffusion process *along the data manifold*, giving the diffusion map its name.

The diffusion map now works by taking a spectral decomposition of the transition matrix M . In order to carry out this step in a computationally efficient manner, we note that M is similar to the matrix

$$M_s = D^{1/2} M D^{-1/2} = D^{-1/2} W^{(\alpha)} D^{-1/2}, \quad (2.8)$$

which is clearly symmetric, since $W^{(\alpha)}$ is also symmetric. We can diagonalize it to arrive at the eigenvalues $\{\lambda_j\}_{j=0}^{N-1}$ and normalized eigenvectors $\{v_j\}_{j=0}^{N-1}$. M has the same eigenvalues as M_s , and we can obtain its left eigenvectors ϕ_j and right eigenvectors ψ_j through a change of basis:

$$\phi_j = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{tr}(D)}} v_j^T D^{1/2}; \quad \psi_j = \sqrt{\text{tr}(D)} D^{-1/2} v_j. \quad (2.9)$$

The prefactors $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{tr}(D)}}$ and $\sqrt{\text{tr}(D)}$ are not usually included in the literature; however, as noted by Beier [27], they are necessary for the diffusion map to fulfill the diffusion distance property. This will be explained in the next subsection and in appendix A.1.

Since the graph defined by M is connected,¹ M describes an irreducible random walk and so has a unique largest eigenvalue of 1. We can therefore order the eigenvalues like

$$1 = |\lambda_0| > |\lambda_1| \geq |\lambda_2| \geq \dots \geq |\lambda_{N-1}| \quad (2.10)$$

The leading left eigenvector ϕ_0 is the stationary distribution of the random walk, whilst its right counterpart is trivial: $\psi_0 = (1, 1, \dots, 1)^T$. What then is the meaning of the other eigenvectors? If we consider a function $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined on the set X of data points, it evolves under the diffusion process defined by M as $f_{t+1} = Mf_t$ and consequently,

$$f_t = M^t f_0. \quad (2.11)$$

If we express f_0 in the eigenbasis of M as $f_0 = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} c_j \psi_j$, then

$$f_t = \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} c_j \lambda_j^t \psi_j. \quad (2.12)$$

The eigenvectors ψ_j therefore represent relaxation modes of the diffusion process, which decay exponentially as $t \rightarrow \infty$, with the only exception of the constant mode with $\lambda_0 = 1$, which remains stable. The leading eigenvectors, which are closest to one, represent the slowest decaying modes and therefore must correspond to the longest length scales of the data manifold. We can therefore assume that these are the eigenvectors which are the most relevant for describing the dataset. Of course, this does not include the first eigenvector ψ_0 , which is constant and thus contains no information. On the other hand, the diffusion components with a smaller eigenvector represent modes with short relaxation times and therefore smaller-scale features, which are likely to be less interesting.

This motivates the following definition of the diffusion map:

$$\Psi_t(\mathbf{x}) = (\lambda_1^t \psi_1(\mathbf{x}), \lambda_2^t \psi_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, \lambda_k^t \psi_k(\mathbf{x})) \quad (2.13)$$

Only the k leading eigenvectors are included, leading to the desired dimensionality reduction when $k < p$. The definition introduces as another parameter the diffusion time $t \geq 0$, which determines which time scale of the diffusion process is being described. The individual components $\lambda_j^t \psi_j$ are also called *diffusion components*.

2.1.1 Diffusion Distance

Another way to motivate the definition of the diffusion map is given by the *diffusion distance*. Let $P_t(x_i|x_j)$ be the probability to jump from data point x_i to x_j under the random

¹The Gaussian kernel never drops to zero, making sure that the graph is always technically connected. Only if, as described above, a threshold is set under which entries of M are set to zero, can it happen that the graph becomes completely disconnected. In that case, the threshold or ϵ are likely not chosen appropriately. If there are clusters in the data, it can also happen that the graph becomes “almost disconnected”, leading to eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots$ which are very close to one.

walk defined by M in exactly t time steps. The diffusion distance D_t between two data points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} is then defined as

$$D_t^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{z \in X} (P_t(z|\mathbf{x}) - P_t(z|\mathbf{y}))^2 w(z). \quad (2.14)$$

where w is the weight function given by $w(z) = 1/\phi_0(z)$. Unlike the Euclidean distance, it depends on all possible paths on the dataset graph between points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} . The diffusion distance can be thought of as a weighted L^2 distance between the probability distributions starting at points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} . It therefore measures how different points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are in terms of the diffusion process at time t . Thanks to the following property, the diffusion map can be thought of as revealing exactly those differences.

When all $N - 1$ components are included in the diffusion map, the Euclidean distance in diffusion map space is equal to the diffusion distance:

$$D_t^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} (\psi_j(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_j(\mathbf{y}))^2 \lambda_j^{2t} \quad (2.15)$$

We shall call this the “diffusion distance property” of the diffusion map in this thesis. A proof is given in section A.1 in the appendix.

Since, in practice, only the first k diffusion components are included in the diffusion map, this does not hold exactly anymore. However, an upper bound for the deviation has been proven by Nadler et al. [15]:

$$\left| D_t^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) - \sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_j^{2t} (\psi_j(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_j(\mathbf{y}))^2 \right| \leq \lambda_{k+1}^{2t} \left(\frac{1}{\phi_0(\mathbf{x})} + \frac{1}{\phi_0(\mathbf{y})} \right) \quad (2.16)$$

This shows that the diffusion distance property can hold to good approximation even for the diffusion map space including only the first k components, if the spectrum λ_j decays fast enough or t is large.

2.1.2 Asymptotics of the Diffusion Map

To interpret the results of the diffusion map, it is helpful to consider how it behaves in the limit of dense data points. This has been considered extensively in the literature [13, 15]. A particularly helpful treatment of this topic has been written by Nadler et al. [28], on which the following remarks are mostly based.

We consider the case where data points lie on some compact manifold $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^p$ and are independently sampled from some probability distribution p . This corresponds to the manifold hypothesis. The interpretation will be helped by assuming that the data points follow a Boltzmann distribution in some potential U : $p(\mathbf{x}) = e^{-U(\mathbf{x})}$. We also assume that Ω , its boundary $\delta\Omega$ and the probability distribution p are sufficiently regular, without going into the details.

We first consider the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$ of dense data points, while ε remains constant. In that limit, the eigenvectors ψ_k become eigenfunctions $\psi_k : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined on the entire

manifold. The transition probabilities likewise become continuous functions on Ω , with the definitions 2.1 - 2.6 completely analogous, e.g.

$$M(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{W^{(\alpha)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})}{D(\mathbf{x})} \quad (2.17)$$

describes the probability to jump from point \mathbf{x} to \mathbf{y} . We can then define the operator

$$T[\psi](\mathbf{x}) = \int_{\Omega} M(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})\psi(\mathbf{y})p(\mathbf{y})d\mathbf{y}, \quad (2.18)$$

which acts on *functions* on Ω analogously to the way that the matrix M acts on column vectors in the discrete case. The eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the discrete matrix M are approximations to those of the continuous operator T . For instance, it is easy to check that the constant function $\psi(\mathbf{x}) = 1$ is an eigenfunction of T . T describes a diffusion process which is continuous in space and discrete in time, with ε designating the time step.

Next, one can consider the limit $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ to arrive at a diffusion process which is also continuous in time. The time evolution $\psi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ of a function is then described by H , the infinitesimal generator of the operator T :

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = H\psi, \quad (2.19)$$

where

$$H = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{T - \text{id}}{\varepsilon}. \quad (2.20)$$

As Coifman and Lafon [13] and Nadler et al. [28] show,

$$H\psi = \Delta\psi - 2(1 - \alpha)\nabla\psi \cdot \nabla U, \quad (2.21)$$

where Δ is the Laplace-Beltrami operator² on Ω , and we recall that $\alpha > 0$ is the normalization parameter introduced in equation 2.4. As shown by Nadler et al. [28], this corresponds to the backward Fokker-Planck equation for a particle in the potential $2(1 - \alpha)U$. We can therefore interpret the diffusion map as the discrete version of a diffusion process in that potential.

This now gives α a concrete meaning: Since U is the potential that describes the varying density of data points, α governs how strongly this density variation influences the diffusion map. When $\alpha = 0$ (the normalization step is skipped), the influence of the varying density is amplified. When $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$, one retrieves the diffusion process in the potential U . Finally, when choosing $\alpha = 1$, H reduces simply to the Laplace-Beltrami operator, removing the influence of the point density. This is of particular interest when the point density is not known to be constant, as is usually the case with natural data. This allows therefore to separate the geometry of Ω from the statistics of the data on Ω . When the density is constant, the infinitesimal generator is always the Laplace-Beltrami operator,

²I use the convention that Δ is negative-definite, in contrast to, e.g., Coifman and Lafon [13]

regardless of the choice of α . However, Coifman and Lafon [13] argue that even in that case, if $\alpha = 0$, slight non-constant modes from random fluctuations are exaggerated.

These limits are useful since they allow us to describe the diffusion components in the limit of dense data points and small ε . In particular, if $\alpha = 1$, or if the density is constant, we know that $T^{\frac{t}{\varepsilon}}$ is an approximation for the operator $e^{t\Delta}$, describing the diffusion process at time t [13]. Therefore, the diffusion components are then identical to the eigenfunctions of Δ , allowing us to calculate them analytically in some simple cases.

One such case is given when the data points lie on a one-dimensional manifold. Following Nadler et al. [15], if $\Gamma : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p$ parametrizes the curve with constant speed, we can calculate the diffusion components by solving the eigenvalue problem

$$H\psi = \frac{d^2\psi}{ds^2} = \mu\psi \quad (2.22)$$

As Coifman and Lafon [13] point out, we need Neumann boundary conditions $\frac{d\psi}{ds}\Big|_{s=0} = \frac{d\psi}{ds}\Big|_{s=1} = 0$ at the edges due to the conservation of probability. The solutions are

$$\psi_l(s) = \cos(l\pi s) \quad (2.23)$$

for $l \in \mathbb{N}$. The eigenvalues of H are given by $\mu_l = -(l\pi)^2$. The first diffusion components are those with the highest (least negative) eigenvalues. After discarding the constant ψ_0 , the first diffusion component ψ_1 provides a one-to-one parametrization of the curve, confirming the utility of the diffusion map in this case. Therefore, all following diffusion components can be expressed in terms of ψ_1 . To be more specific,

$$\psi_l = T_l(\psi_1), \quad (2.24)$$

where T_l is the l -th order Chebyshev polynomial [29]. In particular, the first two diffusion components draw a parabola, characteristic of diffusion map. In this case, all diffusion components but the first are redundant and provide no additional information. This is typical of the diffusion map. After all, when there are as many diffusion components as there are data points, it is clear that most of them are redundant for the purpose of parametrizing the manifold.

Nadler et al. [15] similarly calculate the eigenvalues and eigenfunctions for the case of a rectangle of length L and width H :

$$\mu_{j,k} = -\pi^2 \left(\frac{j^2}{L^2} + \frac{k^2}{H^2} \right) \quad (2.25)$$

$$\psi_{j,k}(t, z) = \cos\left(\frac{j\pi t}{L}\right) \cos\left(\frac{k\pi z}{H}\right), \quad (2.26)$$

with $j, k \in \mathbb{N}$. In this case, it is clearly the eigenfunctions $\psi_{1,0}$ and $\psi_{0,1}$ that parametrize the manifold, encoding the t - and z -directions, respectively. All other components can then again be expressed as functions of those components.

2.1.3 Example: Swiss Roll

To illustrate the diffusion map, I apply it to a classic benchmark for dimensionality reduction algorithms [10, 11, 15]: the Swiss roll dataset, which consists in a two-dimensional sheet which is rolled up in three dimensions. Following Nadler et al. [15], we parametrize it as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} t \cos(t) + \xi_x \\ t \sin(t) + \xi_y \\ z + \xi_z \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.27)$$

where t and z are sampled as $t \sim U\left(\frac{3\pi}{2}, \frac{9\pi}{2}\right)$ and $z \sim U(0, H)$. To make the setting somewhat more realistic, we add some Gaussian noise $\xi \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \text{diag}(\sigma^2, \sigma^2, \sigma^2))$, with $\sigma = 0.2$. If not stated otherwise, $H = 90$ is chosen in the following, because that way, the unrolled sheet is approximately square [15]. The realization of 3000 data points that is used in this thesis is shown in figure 2.1a. The raw data, alongside the implementation of the Diffusion Map and other code for this thesis, is also available in [30].

The simplicity of this toy example allows us to test properties of dimensionality reduction methods in a setting where the desired result is known: Since the data lie close to a two-dimensional manifold, a good dimensionality reduction algorithm should be able to reduce it to two dimensions and approximately map the Swiss roll to a rectangle. The Swiss roll is deliberately constructed to be highly nonlinear, making a nonlinear method necessary to accurately describe it. For instance, points which differ in t by 2π

(a) The Swiss roll dataset.

(b) The first two diffusion components of the Swiss roll. Parameters of the diffusion map: $\varepsilon = 5$, $\alpha = 1$, $t = 1$.

Figure 2.1: The Swiss roll and its diffusion map embedding. The coloring of the points is according to the parameter t in equation 2.27. In this case, the diffusion map is clearly able to parametrize the Swiss roll in terms of its underlying coordinates.

are geometrically quite close together in feature space, but the shortest path *along the manifold* involves taking a full revolution about the origin, making them farther away in embedding space.

Figure 2.1b shows the first two components of the diffusion map of the Swiss roll. In this case, the diffusion map is well able to uncover the two underlying dimensions. They correspond to the first two diffusion components. There is only some slight distortion. For one, data points lie closer together on the inner part of the Swiss roll, apparently due to the higher sample density there.³ Even though $\alpha = 1$ was used, which should mitigate this density effect, it seems that a slight distortion remains. It is also noticeable that in the diffusion map, there are large empty pockets with no data points, which are not present in the original data. This is most likely due to random variations in the sample density, which get exaggerated by the diffusion map, causing data points to bunch closer together.

We shall encounter the example of the Swiss roll throughout the rest of this thesis, whenever an example dataset is needed.

2.1.4 Parameter Selection and Data Preparation

Before applying the diffusion map in practice, a number of choices must be made. The most important parameter is the kernel width ϵ . Too small, and some points can become practically disconnected from the rest of the graph, so that they cannot be reached by the random walk. Too large, and the random walk is not local anymore, spoiling the nonlinear nature of the diffusion map. On the example of the Swiss roll, for instance, this would be the case if ϵ was large enough to bridge the gap between adjacent layers. A number of methods therefore exist to choose ϵ appropriately. For instance, one can try to identify the typical distance between close neighbors and choose ϵ accordingly [31]. Other, more sophisticated methods are based on a scaling argument [26] or a semigroup property [23]. In practice, one can also tune ϵ manually, by simply calculating the diffusion map for different values of ϵ and comparing the results. A value of ϵ that is too small can be identified by the presence of unexpected clusters. One can use that to choose ϵ “as small as possible and as large as necessary”.

The diffusion time t governs the time frame at which the diffusion process is represented. While this has a strong effect on the spectrum of the diffusion map and the diffusion distance, this is not of big interest when the purpose of the diffusion map is to obtain a parametrization of the data manifold. As we can see from the definition of the diffusion map (2.13), it simply results in a scaling of the diffusion components. In this thesis, $t = 1$ is therefore always used.

Since the diffusion map relies on the Euclidean distance in the original data space, it is sensitive to scaling of the dimensions relative to each other. Scaling up one component of the input dataset before calculating the diffusion map increases its relative importance. The feature obscuration as presented in section 2.1.6 can be a consequence of this. It is therefore important to consider the scale of the various input variables. When all the

³The underlying coordinate t is sampled uniformly, but it is not equal to the arc length along the spiral. This results in a higher sample density on the inner part of the spiral, where it is more tightly coiled.

variables of the dataset naturally represent different components of a Euclidean space, this might not be of such concern. This will be the case for instance for an image dataset, where every component represents the brightness of a pixel. However, if different variables are inherently not comparable to one another, it needs to be decided how they should be scaled relative to each other. For instance, this will be the case for a dataset where the variables measure concentrations of various substances which are all on different orders of magnitude, or for a dataset where the measurements are in different units altogether. In those cases, it is common [21, 22] to standardize the dataset before computing the diffusion map. This means that each of the p components of the input dataset is shifted and rescaled to have a mean of zero and variance of one, in an attempt to make sure that they all have the same importance.

2.1.5 Out-of-Sample Extension and the Pre-Image Problem

Just like other spectral dimensionality reduction methods, the diffusion map is a nonparametric method. It is only defined on the given data points and does not define a function $\mathbb{R}^p \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^k$. Therefore, if for example new data points are introduced, the diffusion map is not defined on them. Recomputing the diffusion map is computationally expensive and leads to an entirely different mapping, which may not be comparable. It is therefore desirable to approximately extend the diffusion map to data points which are not part of the original sample, a problem called *out-of-sample extension*. Several methods exist to address this problem, the most popular being the Nyström extension [32]. Other methods, such as Geometric Harmonics [33] and a method based on Laplacian pyramids [34] have also been proposed.

Conversely, an “inverse diffusion map” $\Psi^{-1} : \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p$ is also not defined. However, when performing operations in the diffusion map space, it would of course be helpful to be able to pull them back into the original space. The problem to approximate an inverse, called the *pre-image problem*, has also been treated in the literature, usually with focus on Kernel PCA [35–37].

2.1.6 Feature Obscuration

One peculiar property of the diffusion map, which I suggest might be called *feature obscuration*, has been briefly mentioned by Nadler et al. [15], but has otherwise received little attention. As already mentioned, most of the many diffusion components represent redundant information, and the most relevant ones tend to be the first few components with the largest eigenvalues. While this is generally true, it is not necessarily the case that, for some k , the first consecutive k components all contribute meaningful information, while all subsequent components are redundant.

An example based on the Swiss roll will elucidate this phenomenon. Equation 2.26 tells us the diffusion components and the order of their eigenvalues, provided that data points are dense enough and ϵ is small enough. Component $\psi_{1,0}$ encodes the t -direction while component $\psi_{0,1}$ encodes the z -direction of the Swiss roll (see equation 2.27). Together,

Figure 2.2: Diffusion map of Swiss roll datasets of varying heights H (from top to bottom). Each subplot shows the first diffusion component plotted against one of the other leading diffusion components $\psi_2 \dots \psi_5$ (from left to right). The color represents the z parameter (see equation 2.27), relative to the entire height of the Swiss roll. Parameters of the diffusion map: $\epsilon = 5, \alpha = 1$

they offer a one-to-one parametrization of the Swiss roll. To see if these two components actually appear as the first ones when calculating the diffusion map, we assume that $L > H$ and consider the order in which the eigenvalues according to equation 2.26 appear. Clearly, the first non-trivial eigenfunction is $\psi_{1,0}$ ($\psi_{0,0}$ of course getting discarded by the diffusion map). To see when $\psi_{0,1}$ appears, we compare its eigenvalue to the eigenvalue of $\psi_{k,0}$, which is a higher-order eigenfunction corresponding to the t -direction. We can see from equation 2.26 that the $(k,0)$ component appears before the $(0,1)$ component if $L > kH$. So the first component that offers information about the smaller direction appears as the second diffusion component only if the aspect ratio is less than 2:1. It gets pushed back further the more unequal the ratio is.

Figure 2.2 illustrates this phenomenon in practice. It shows the first few diffusion components of Swiss roll datasets of three different heights (50, 35 and 20). Recall that $L \approx 90$. The figure confirms the preceding predictions. The Swiss rolls have length to height ratios of around 1.8, 2.6 and 4.5, and the z -direction therefore shows up in the second, third and fifth diffusion component, respectively.

When looking at just the first two diffusion components of one of the narrower Swiss rolls, the characteristic parabola could lead one to wrongly conclude that the manifold is

one-dimensional. Thus, care must be taken to also look at higher-order components to get a fuller picture. We will see whether feature obscuration can also occur in real-life datasets.

2.2 Deep Neural Networks

Neural networks are powerful and versatile tools, with applications in many fields. As much as there is to say about them, this section will contain only a brief introduction of the concepts needed for this thesis. The focus will therefore be on fully connected feedforward networks used for regression tasks. All of the following concepts and many more are covered in the relevant literature [8, 38].

In a regression task, the goal is to approximate some function $f : \mathbb{R}^k \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p$. No closed form of f is known; in fact, it is questionable if it even exists. The model is instead tasked with finding an approximation, given a large amount of value pairs $(x_i, y_i = f(x_i))$. The model achieves this by realizing a function \hat{f}_θ that depends on a large parameter set θ ; the training examples are used to find a θ so that \hat{f}_θ approximates f as best as possible.

A feedforward network can be thought of as consisting of several layers. Each layer takes as input the output from the previous layer, called activation, and returns its own output. The activations $a_l \in \mathbb{R}^{k_l}$ of layer l are calculated by applying an affine linear transformation, followed by an element-wise application of the nonlinear activation function g : $a_l = g(W^l a_{l-1} + b^l)$. Here, W^l is a matrix of weights and b^l a vector of biases associated with layer l . The weights and biases of all layers form the parameter vector θ which is meant to be optimized during training. The activations of the first layer are set to the input x , while the activations of the final layer a_L are the output of the network. The intermediate layers are called hidden layers; their number and respective dimensions k_l are the so-called model hyperparameters that are fixed during training. Figure 2.3 shows an illustration of a small neural network. Each element of each layer is depicted as an individual node, called neuron. The arrows represent the different weights. A network like this is also called fully connected, since every node is connected by a weight to every node in the neighboring layers.

The purpose of the activation function g is to introduce a nonlinearity, so that the network would be able to also learn nonlinear functions. Many different activation functions are used; one of the more common choices is called ReLU, short for “rectified linear unit”. It is the piecewise linear function $\text{ReLU}(z) = \max(0, z)$. It has proven to perform well, while being very cheap computationally, and is therefore very popular [8].

The quality of the approximation is quantified by the cost function, also called the loss function. The obvious choice for regression tasks, which we shall use, is the mean squared error $C(\theta) = \frac{1}{Np} \sum_{i=1}^N \|\hat{f}_\theta(x_i) - y_i\|^2$. Here, the summation is over all the examples in the training dataset. The task is therefore a minimization problem where the value of θ must be found that minimizes the cost function. Since the parameter space is huge and the cost function is non-convex, finding the global minimum is hopeless. However, the gradient $\frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta}$ can be calculated quite easily by applying the chain rule through all layers

Figure 2.3: Illustration of a neural network. In this example, the input layer has dimension 2, the output layer has dimension 3, and there are two hidden layers of width 5. Image generated using the handy tool NN-SVG [39].

(backpropagation). Local minima can therefore be iteratively approximated using gradient descent, where at each step, the parameters are adjusted in the direction of maximum decrease: $\theta_{i+1} = \theta_i - \eta \left. \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta} \right|_{\theta_i}$. The learning rate η is another, crucial, hyperparameter that must be decided. In practice, since the cost function involves evaluating the neural network at all points in the training dataset, the full cost function is not used. Instead, at each step, the gradient is approximated using a partial cost function, involving a small subset of a few training data points, called a mini-batch. This is called stochastic gradient descent, or, more specifically, batch gradient descent. In practice, many variants of this algorithm exist [40]. One of the more popular ones is called Adam [41], featuring also a momentum-like dynamic and adaptive learning rates. This is the optimization algorithm used in this thesis, since it is known for its good performance and is often recommended as the default choice [40].

During training, minibatches are drawn at random from the entire training dataset without replacement until all data points have been shown to the network exactly once. One such period is called an epoch. This process repeats for a number of epochs; the duration of the training is typically given in this unit.

In principle, a sufficiently large (in terms of the number and size of hidden layers) network is able to approximate any continuous function to arbitrary accuracy [42]. The ability of a neural network to approximate a large set of functions is also called its *capacity*. However, if training data is limited, in particular if the number of parameters is larger than or on the same order of magnitude as the number of points in the training dataset, one incurs the risk of overfitting. This describes the failure of the network to generalize to unseen data; instead, the training data is only “memorized”. In order to identify overfitting, the available data is split into a training dataset and a typically much smaller test dataset, which the network does not see during training. After training, the network’s performance is then evaluated on the test dataset. Overfitting can be identified by a loss

which is much smaller on the training dataset than on the test dataset. A number of regularization techniques exist to help limit this phenomenon. One of the most common ones, which is also applied in this thesis, is called L^2 regularization, whereby a small regularization term $\frac{\beta}{2} \sum_i \theta_i^2$ is added to the cost function. β is a, typically small, parameter, also called weight decay, that governs the regularization term. The idea is to make sure that the network does not put too much weight on the examples it sees in the hope that it improves the performance on the examples it does not see.

The training process involves many hyperparameters, called training hyperparameters, that affect the way the network learns. They include the learning rate, the size of the mini-batches, the weight decay β , and the duration of the training in epochs. The learning rate is probably the most crucial of these hyperparameters [8]. If it is too small, training might be too slow or the network might get stuck in a local minimum, halting progress altogether. If it is too large, one can expect large fluctuations or even divergent behavior. Instead of a fixed learning rate, it is common to employ a learning rate schedule, whereby the learning rate decreases over time. This allows the training to progress quickly in the early stages, while finer adjustments can be made later in training. In this thesis, two kinds of learning rate schedule are employed: The stepwise learning rate scheduler reduces the learning rate by a factor of γ every certain number of epochs, given by the step size. It is also possible to reduce the learning rate once training stagnates (Reduce learning rate on plateau). This scheduler is governed by three parameters: The threshold indicates the relative improvement in the cost function below which it is considered a plateau. The patience indicates for how many epochs the plateau is allowed to continue before the learning rate is reduced. The reduction factor indicates by how much the learning rate is reduced.

Before training can commence, suitable values for both the model and training hyperparameters must be found. This is called tuning.

3 The Neural Reconstruction Error

In the introduction to the diffusion map in section 2.1, one particular issue is glanced over: The diagonalization of the transition matrix M offers up to $N - 1$ diffusion components, as many as there are data points. In order to reduce the dimensionality of the dataset, we retain only the first k diffusion components, where we have to choose k . As argued in section 2.1, it is generally reasonable to expect that the diffusion components with the largest eigenvalues are the most relevant. However, there is little in the way of justification for the exact choice of k . In applications of the diffusion map, this aspect is often neglected. Some works refer to the spectrum in order to motivate their choice of k [18, 19]. As will be laid out in the following section, this approach is flawed, since the spectrum cannot be relied upon to measure the quality of a diffusion map. In other works, the authors rely on what they expect the dimensionality of the dataset to be, or what features they would like to see represented [16, 20, 22]. A surprising amount of works simply show the first two or three diffusion components without mentioning why [17, 21, 43]. It appears that in many cases, this is done for the sole reason that two or three diffusion components is the maximum number that can be conveniently visualized in a scatter plot. While understandable, this is of course not a sufficient justification.

What we therefore need is a way to measure the quality of a diffusion map, i.e. how much information from the original dataset is preserved. One could then use this measure to argue why a certain number of diffusion components may be used to describe a dataset. This would also offer a systematic way of choosing k , by setting some threshold, and keeping the minimum number of components that performs at least as well as this threshold. In some applications, e.g. classification tasks, such a quality measure may already be provided by the accuracy of the classification. However, this is not the case when the goal of the diffusion map is to identify relevant coordinates. In that case, it is crucial to know how much of the information in the dataset is preserved by the diffusion components. For that, there currently exists no universally accepted measure.

This chapter is dedicated to finding a suitable quality measure. Section 3.1 focuses on the spectrum of the diffusion map, which has been suggested as such. I will outline how this is motivated and present evidence that it is unsuitable for this purpose. Section 3.2 explores different quality metrics that have been used for dimensionality reduction methods in general. Finally, in section 3.3, I propose the Neural Reconstruction Error, a new quality measure that can be used for the diffusion map, but also for other dimensionality reduction methods. The subsequent sections are dedicated to the technical details and interpretation of the Neural Reconstruction Error.

3.1 The Spectrum as a Quality Metric for the Diffusion Map

The distinguishing feature of the diffusion map is the diffusion distance property (see section 2.1.1). It is therefore natural to first turn to this property to measure the quality of a diffusion map. Equation 2.16 gives us an upper bound for the deviation between the Euclidean distance in the first k diffusion components and the true diffusion distance. Crucially, this bound is proportional to λ_{k+1}^{2t} . The spectrum $\{\lambda_j^t\}_{j \geq 1}$ can therefore tell us how accurately the diffusion distance is reflected in the diffusion map. This is why most of the discussion around the accuracy of diffusion map has centered around this spectrum [13, 15, 25]. For instance, Coifman and Lafon [13] have suggested to set some threshold $\delta > 0$ and to retain all diffusion components ψ_j whose eigenvalues satisfy $|\lambda_j|^t > \delta |\lambda_1|^t$.

Of course, the spectrum λ_j^t is highly dependent on t . This makes sense, since the diffusion distance measures the similarity of data points through the lens of a diffusion process *at timescale* t . While this may be of interest to describe the different timescales at which the diffusion modes decay, for the purposes of dimensionality reduction, the choice of t proves to be problematic. For small t , even points that are reasonably close together have a very high diffusion distance, since the probability distributions starting at those points barely intersect. On the other extreme, for very large t , the diffusion process is already close to equilibrium, so that the diffusion distance between all points is small. There is no indication as to what intermediate timescale should be chosen to extract the interesting features of the dataset. This is reflected in figure 3.1. It shows the spectrum λ^t for the diffusion map of the Swiss roll (see section 2.1.3). Recall that the first two diffusion components provide a parametrization of the manifold, with all subsequent components being redundant. As one would expect, the decay of the spectrum is highly dependent on the value of t . The procedure suggested by Coifman and Lafon [13] therefore yields very different values of k depending on the timescale used. That way, one could justify any value of k by appropriately tuning t . Looking at figure 3.1, we also note that there is no spectral gap after the first two components, even though we know these are the only relevant ones for parametrizing the manifold. The spectrum is therefore not a suitable accuracy metric for the diffusion map, when the goal is manifold learning.

Figure 3.1: Spectrum λ_j^t of the diffusion map of Swiss roll for different values of t .

3.2 Quality Metrics for General Dimensionality Reduction Methods

Measuring the quality of dimensionality reduction methods is of course not a new problem. A wealth of different metrics exists, which is fueled by the fact that the task of dimensionality reduction is not well-defined [44]. There can therefore not be a universal objective measure for the quality of a mapping. Depending on the dataset and goal of the dimensionality reduction, different properties might be desirable [6]. Many dimensionality reduction methods are based on optimizing their own objective function, such as Multidimensional Scaling [45], t-SNE and Isomap. In that case, it is natural to use the respective objective function as a metric for the quality of an embedding. The diffusion map can also be seen as an optimization problem, as the eigenvalue decomposition can be framed as such [3]. However, the objective function reduces to the spectrum,¹ which suffers from the drawbacks outlined in the previous section.

Of course, the method-specific metrics do not provide a fair comparison between different dimensionality reduction techniques. Method-agnostic metrics have therefore been developed. Some metrics are based on comparing the matrices of pairwise distances D and D' between data points in the original space and the embedding, respectively. The entries of D and D' may be Euclidean distances or based on any other distance function. They can be qualitatively compared in a scatterplot, called *Shepard diagram* [44], or their values can be summarized in a scalar, such as the normalized stress [44] or the Spearman or Pearson correlation coefficient. The latter is used to define what in the context of Isomap or Multidimensional Scaling is called the residual variance $1 - R^2(D, D')$ [11], although caution is advised since this is not equivalent to the unexplained variance in the context of PCA, which can also be called residual variance.

There is also a whole family of metrics based on ranked pairwise distances, which can be summarized by the co-ranking matrix framework [46]. Instead of the pairwise distances D_{ij} , we consider their ranks r_{ij} . We define r_{ij} as the rank of x_j in terms of the distance to x_i :

$$r_{ij} = \#\{k : D_{ik} < D_{ij}\}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\#$ stands for the set cardinality.² Analogously, r'_{ij} is defined for the distances between the mapped points $\Psi(x)$:

$$r'_{ij} = \#\{k : D'_{ik} < D'_{ij}\} \quad (3.2)$$

The co-ranking matrix Q is then defined as an $N \times N$ matrix with elements

$$Q_{kl} = \#\{(i, j) : r_{ij} = k \text{ and } r'_{ij} = l\}. \quad (3.3)$$

¹As noted by Ghojogh et al. [3] in section 9.7.2, the diffusion map is the solution to the maximization problem: Find $\Psi \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times k}$ with $\Psi^T \Psi = \mathbb{1}$ such that $\text{tr}(\Psi^T M^t \Psi)$ is maximized. The columns of Ψ are then the first k diffusion components, and $\text{tr}(\Psi^T M^t \Psi) = \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \lambda_j^t$.

²This is a slight simplification. The actual definition is slightly more involved to account for tied distances. Refer to Lee and Verleysen [46] for the details.

In words, Q is a joint histogram of the ranked distances in both the original data space and the embedding, and Q_{kl} tells us how many points of distance rank k in the original space have distance rank l in the embedding. Since it is a matrix, it is much more difficult to interpret and compare than a scalar metric.

A number of metrics therefore exist which can be thought of as summarizing the co-ranking matrix in a scalar. They include the Trustworthiness and Continuity measures, Mean Relative Rank Errors or the Local Continuity Meta-Criterion (LCMC) [46]. They measure slightly different aspects of the embedding; in practice, it can be difficult to decide which of these metrics to use. It also appears that their definitions are rather heuristic. It is usually easy to see that a “perfect” embedding scores very well. However, it is not clear how meaningful these metrics are for imperfect embeddings.

The LCMC, for instance [47], is defined as

$$U_{LC}(K) = \frac{1}{NK} \sum_{i,j=0}^K Q_{ij} - \frac{K}{N-1}. \quad (3.4)$$

It measures the proportion of K -nearest neighbor pairs in the original data space that remain K -nearest neighbors in the embedding. The second term removes the baseline that would be expected for a random embedding. It is clear that the LCMC measures a desirable property – preserving K -neighborhoods of the data. However, it is questionable how well this describes the overall quality of a dimensionality reduction. For instance, point pairs which are nearest neighbors in the original data and K -nearest neighbors in the embedding count positively towards the LCMC. At the same time, point pairs which go from being K -nearest neighbors to being $(K+1)$ -nearest neighbors are penalized, even though arguably, this is a much more harmless deviation [48].

A more principled metric would therefore be desirable. For dimensionality reduction methods which provide an inverse mapping, one option is the mean squared *reconstruction error*. For some mapping Ψ it is defined as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{p} \left\langle \|\Psi^{-1}(\Psi(\mathbf{x})) - \mathbf{x}\|^2 \right\rangle = \frac{1}{Np} \sum_{i=1}^N \|\Psi^{-1}(\Psi(\mathbf{x}_i)) - \mathbf{x}_i\|^2, \quad (3.5)$$

where the averaging $\langle \cdot \rangle$ refers to averaging over the dataset. Its definition is straightforward, having an intuitive interpretation: If the mapping Ψ is well suited to describe the data, it preserves a lot of information about the original data, hence it is possible to reconstruct it from the embedding. For instance, if the data lie on a submanifold of \mathbb{R}^p , and Ψ provides a chart, then in principle, it is possible to reconstruct the original manifold with perfect accuracy: $\varepsilon = 0$. If however a lot of information is missing in Ψ , then the reconstruction error will be larger, indicating a lower accuracy of the embedding. The reconstruction error has therefore been considered an obvious and fair quality measure in the literature, in cases where the inverse mapping is available [46, 49, 50]. However, most nonlinear dimensionality reduction methods, including the diffusion map, are non-parametric and as such do not provide an inverse mapping. This criterion is therefore not widely used [46].

3.3 Introducing the Neural Reconstruction Error

Given the clear advantages of the reconstruction error as a quality metric, it would be desirable to extend it to dimensionality reduction techniques where the inverse does not exist. I propose a scheme that does exactly that, which can be used for the diffusion map or any other dimensionality reduction method. The idea is that the inverse transformation is replaced by an approximate inverse, which is learned by a neural network.

A feedforward network receives the diffusion map coordinates $\{\Psi_{(k)}(x_i)\}$ as inputs and original data points $\{x_i\}$ as targets, thus learning an approximate inverse mapping $\hat{\Psi}_{(k)}^{-1}$. Here, the subscript k is included to stress that the diffusion map includes the first k components. The reconstruction error is used as the cost function, such that the network will aim to minimize it. After training, the reconstruction error can be evaluated on the dataset, using the approximate inverse mapping learned by the network:

$$\varepsilon_k = \frac{1}{p} \left\langle \left\| \hat{\Psi}_{(k)}^{-1}(\Psi_{(k)}(x)) - x \right\|^2 \right\rangle = \frac{1}{Np} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \hat{\Psi}_{(k)}^{-1}(\Psi_{(k)}(x_i)) - x_i \right\|^2. \quad (3.6)$$

This is the k -dependent reconstruction error ε_k , which I will call the *Neural Reconstruction Error (NRE)*. This quantity can then be used to draw conclusions about the dataset and the performance of the diffusion map. For instance, one could set a threshold (e.g. $\varepsilon_k < 0.1$) before calculating the NRE to find the smallest k that achieves the desired precision. Alternatively, one could identify kinks in the function ε_k in order to try and estimate the intrinsic dimensionality of the data.

Figure 3.2 illustrates the NRE schematically. A reader who is familiar with neural networks will immediately recognize the similarity to autoencoders. In fact, the NRE structure is identical to an autoencoder, where the encoder has been replaced with the diffusion map. Note that none of the steps described above depend on Ψ being the diffusion map, so that any other dimensionality reduction method could also be used instead. NRE analysis can therefore be used to evaluate any dimensionality reduction method and also for comparing different dimensionality reduction methods to each other.

The following sections will focus first on the implementation details and then on the interpretation of the NRE.

Figure 3.2: Schematic illustration of the Neural Reconstruction Error

3.4 Training of the Decoders

The decoders are trained using a straightforward supervised learning approach: The model is as described in section 2.2, a feedforward neural network with fully connected layers and ReLU activations at each layer. The training dataset consists of the diffusion map coordinates $\{\Psi(x_i)\}$ as inputs and the original data points $\{x_i\}$ as targets. The cost function is given by the mean squared reconstruction error, plus the L^2 regularizer term:

$$C(\theta) = \frac{1}{p} \langle \|\hat{\Psi}_\theta^{-1}(\Psi(\mathbf{x})) - \mathbf{x}\|^2 \rangle + \frac{\beta}{2} \sum_i \theta_i^2, \quad (3.7)$$

where the elements θ_i refer to the individual weights and biases of the network. The L^2 regularization is of course optional; in the numerical experiments in this thesis, a very small value was always used for β ($\beta = 10^{-6}$), so that its influence is limited.

As in any application of neural networks, the model and training hyperparameters need to be tuned to suitable values. In this thesis, ReLU is always used as the activation function, as it is a popular choice and well known to deliver good results [8]. Limited tests showed no notable difference in performance when using other common activation functions such as sigmoid or the hyperbolic tangent. As for the number and width of layers, a balance needs to be struck. In general, a larger network is more powerful. However, in practice, increasing the layer widths or number of layers may not always result in an improvement. Not only does it increase the time needed for training, it also increases the risk of overfitting, which can result in a worse overall performance. For the numerical experiments in this thesis, manual tuning was used. The layer widths and number of layers are varied separately, at each step settling on the version that yields the lowest error. The training hyperparameters are tuned in a similar fashion. This concerns the training rate schedule and duration of the training.

Tuning has to be done separately for each application of the NRE in order to ensure that the network has sufficient capacity for the dataset at hand, while keeping the computational cost of the training reasonable. The hyperparameters used in the numerical experiments to follow are listed in the appendix. Of course, all hyperparameters need to be identical for a given dataset, in order to ensure the comparability of the reconstruction errors for the different input components. Tuning should be performed for the largest network, in order to ensure that the networks have sufficient capacity to learn the reconstruction even in the most complex case. If, for instance, the NRE should be calculated for the first 10 diffusion components, then the network that uses all 10 diffusion components as input should be tuned and the resulting parameters used for all networks for the same dataset.

In principle, more sophisticated methods for hyperparameter tuning, such as a grid search or Bayesian optimization [51], could be used to obtain better performance. However, the performance improvements diminish strongly as more effort is put into hyperparameter optimization. In fact, during tuning, it appeared that the reconstruction error is not very sensitive to changes in model hyperparameters within a considerable range. Moreover, as the same hyperparameters are used for the training for all values of

k , comparative conclusions can still be drawn, even if the performance of the networks is not optimal. Since optimizing the tuning further is not the focus of this thesis, I decided against using more advanced method in the examples to follow. Potentially, however, this could be a further avenue for making the NRE more robust and easier to use.

As for the implementation, the PyTorch [52] library is used for all training. The source code can be found in [30]. The runtime for training a network depends on the size of the network and the dataset; for the examples in this thesis, training usually took around one to ten minutes on an ordinary consumer laptop for one decoder, i.e. calculating a single reconstruction error. This is considerably slower than other quality measures for dimensionality reduction. However, it is not so slow as to make NRE impractical to use.

3.5 Quantitative Interpretation of the Neural Reconstruction Error

One of the key advantages of the NRE is that we can interpret it quantitatively. Using an appropriate normalization, this allows for an intuitive summary of the quality of a diffusion map, comparable to the variance unexplained of PCA.

Normalized Neural Reconstruction Error

To interpret the NRE ε_k quantitatively, it is straightforward to normalize it to ε_0 . When $k = 0$, the neural network is trained without any inputs. In that case, it is forced to make the same prediction for every point, and the reconstruction error is clearly minimized when the prediction is equal to the mean of the original dataset, making the use of a neural network unnecessary:

$$\hat{\Psi}^{-1}(\mathbf{y}) = \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle, \quad \text{independently of } \mathbf{y} \quad (3.8)$$

In that case, the reconstruction error is simply the variance of the dataset, in the sense of the average variance of each component:

$$\varepsilon_0 = \frac{1}{p} \langle \|\hat{\Psi}^{-1}(\Psi(\mathbf{x})) - \mathbf{x}\|^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{p} \langle \|\langle \mathbf{x} \rangle - \mathbf{x}\|^2 \rangle = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{i=1}^p \text{Var}(x_i) \quad (3.9)$$

Normalizing the NRE to ε_0 makes it take values from 0 (perfect reconstruction) to 1 (complete loss of information):

$$\varepsilon_{k,\text{norm}} = \frac{\varepsilon_k}{\varepsilon_0} \quad (3.10)$$

This step is of course unnecessary if the data was standardized before applying diffusion map, as described in section 2.1.4. In the following, unless stated otherwise, reported NRE values will always refer to the NRE which is normalized in the aforementioned way.

The Reconstruction Error of PCA

In order to draw a comparison with a familiar method, we calculate the reconstruction error for PCA. PCA already has an inverse transformation Ψ^{-1} , and the calculation of the reconstruction error is straightforward: Assuming mean zero, PCA just consists in applying an orthogonal transformation W :

$$\mathbf{y} = \Psi(\mathbf{x}) = W\mathbf{x} \quad (3.11)$$

The inverse transformation is therefore obtained by applying W^T :

$$\Psi^{-1}(\mathbf{y}) = W^T\mathbf{y} \quad (3.12)$$

The dimensionality reduction consists in keeping only the first k components of the transformed vector \mathbf{y} :

$$y_i^{(k)} = \begin{cases} y_i, & \text{if } i \leq k \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.13)$$

Therefore, the reconstruction error of a data point \mathbf{x} is simply given by all the components that were omitted:

$$\|\Psi^{-1}(\mathbf{y}^{(k)}) - \mathbf{x}\|^2 = \sum_{i=k+1}^p y_i^2 \quad (3.14)$$

So the reconstruction error for the dataset is just

$$\varepsilon_k = \left\langle \sum_{i=k+1}^p y_i^2 \right\rangle = \sum_{i=k+1}^p \lambda_i, \quad (3.15)$$

the unexplained variance. Here, $\langle \cdot \rangle$ again refers to the mean over all data points and the λ_i refer to the eigenvalues of the covariance matrix, which in the context of PCA are also referred to as the ‘‘variance explained’’. The normalization of the NRE then corresponds to normalizing the eigenvectors λ_i by the total variance, leading to the commonly used relative explained variance. In particular, the reconstruction error for PCA is just one minus the relative explained variance, confirming the intuitive meaning of the reconstruction error. This enables us to directly compare the accuracy of diffusion map in terms of the NRE with PCA.

In PCA, the eigenvalues can be obtained from the reconstruction accuracy as

$$\lambda_k = \varepsilon_{k-1} - \varepsilon_k, \quad (3.16)$$

i.e. the improvement made by including the k th component. In principle, we could define by analogy for the diffusion map

$$r_k = \varepsilon_{k-1} - \varepsilon_k, \quad (3.17)$$

a quantity measuring the importance of a single diffusion component, analogous to the eigenvalues of PCA. However, the interpretation of this quantity is not quite as straightforward, since it depends on all diffusion components, not just the one at hand. This will become particularly clear in section 3.8.

Finally, the difference between the reconstruction error and the *Neural* Reconstruction Error of PCA should be highlighted. The above reconstruction does not require a neural network, since an explicit inverse transformation is given for PCA. However, it is still possible to instead train a neural decoder in the same way as for the diffusion map. If the data follow a multivariate normal distribution, the resulting reconstruction error will be the same (apart from noise), since the inverse transformation of PCA minimizes the reconstruction error in that case. However, for general distributions, the principal components, though linearly *uncorrelated*, are not necessarily *independent*. It can therefore still make sense to calculate NREs of a PCA; the reconstruction errors will in general be smaller, since the neural network can exploit the interdependence of principal components to make more accurate predictions. The NRE should also be used when comparing PCA to another method, in order to get a fair comparison. We will see the difference between both reconstruction errors in practice on some of the example datasets.

3.6 Example: Swiss Roll

In order to see how the NRE works in practice, let us return to the diffusion map of the Swiss roll, as seen in section 2.1.3. Figure 3.3 shows the NRE of that diffusion map as a function of the number of included components. The parameters which were used for training the decoders are listed in table A.2 in the appendix. The NRE drops to almost zero once the first two components are included, indicating clearly that they parametrize the manifold completely. This is intuitive, confirming what we saw about the diffusion map of the Swiss roll in section 2.1.3. The drop corresponding to ψ_1 is smaller than the one for ψ_2 simply because the former encodes the t -direction of the Swiss roll (see equation 2.27), along which the manifold is rolled up. The Euclidean distances in the data space are therefore smaller than the geodesic distances along the manifold. The reconstruction error, however, is defined in terms of the Euclidean distances, which should be borne in mind when interpreting the NRE.

We can compare this result to other measures for the quality of the diffusion map. The spectrum of the diffusion map in figure 3.1 on page 24 shows no indication that two diffusion components are sufficient to map the manifold. It offers no quantitative indication as to the quality of the embedding. The Local Continuity Meta Criterion of the same diffusion map is shown in figure 3.4 and serves as an example of the metrics based on the co-ranking framework. Here, $K = 10$ was chosen as the neighborhood size; other values give the same qualitative result. It already appears more useful: There is a large difference in LCMC between including one diffusion component versus two. The plateau after $k = 2$ indicates that the quality of the embedding does not improve when

Figure 3.3: NRE of the diffusion map of the Swiss roll as a function of the number of diffusion components.

Figure 3.4: LCMC (equation 3.4) of the diffusion map of the Swiss roll as a function of the number of diffusion components. Here, $K = 10$ was used for the neighborhood size. Values calculated using the implementation by Kraemer et al. [49].

including more than two components. However, the LCMC does not get very close to one, suggesting that the embedding is not ideal. As we have seen, though, the diffusion map with two components is perfectly suitable to parametrize the Swiss roll. It therefore appears that the LCMC is difficult to interpret quantitatively. This shows how the NRE offers advantages over rank-based metrics.

3.7 Related Approaches

This is not the first time that diffusion maps and neural networks have been combined. Mishne et al. [53] introduce what they coin “diffusion nets”. A feedforward network, called the encoder, is trained to reproduce the diffusion map. This makes it possible to perform out-of-sample extension of the diffusion map, allowing to extend it to data points without re-calculating the entire diffusion map. Given how computationally expensive diffusion map is, this can be useful for very large datasets or in on-line settings where data points become available one by one. Similarly, a decoder is trained to solve the pre-image problem, i.e. to reconstruct the original data from the diffusion components. The encoder and decoder can then be stacked to form an autoencoder, which can be used for denoising or outlier detection. Building on that, Dorado et al. [25] construct a “deep diffusion autoencoder”, where the training of the encoder and decoder happens simultaneously.

The setup in this thesis is therefore equivalent to the one in the aforementioned sources, except that the diffusion map is left as-is and not replaced by a neural network. However, the goal in these papers is not to measure the quality of the diffusion map. In both sources, the embedding dimension is fixed, with little justification as to the choice of this dimension. In fact, they also make reference to using the eigenvalues of the diffusion map to judge the importance of the components.

The most similar concept I could find to the Neural Reconstruction Error is the Data Space Reconstruction Error (DSRE) used by Meier and Kramer [6] and Kramer [54]. This is another measure for the quality of dimensionality reduction methods, which, however, does not seem to have found widespread adoption. Like the NRE, it is also an extension of the reconstruction error for situations where an inverse mapping is not available. For this purpose, a K -nearest neighbors regression is used, instead of the supervised learning in this thesis. This builds more on the local structure and makes the DSRE deterministic and more computationally efficient than the NRE. However, it is also subject to the choice of the neighborhood size K . This might prove problematic in the case of highly varying data density or highly nonlinear data manifolds. Comparing the two approaches in depth could be the subject of future work.

3.8 Combinations of Nonconsecutive Diffusion Components

Components

The feature obscuration mentioned in section 2.1.6 provides a challenge for the NRE approach. Let us return to the example of the narrow Swiss roll already mentioned in that section. The diffusion map of the Swiss roll of width 20 is shown again in figure 3.5. The components ψ_1 and ψ_5 encode the t - and z -coordinates, respectively. Diffusion components 2 through 4, however, turn out to be essentially polynomials of the first diffusion component. They provide next to no information which is not already contained in ψ_1 . The NRE picture (figure 3.6) reflects that. There is a significant decrease in the reconstruction error when the first component and the fifth component are first included. Adding diffusion components two to four does not yield an improvement, as indicated by the plateau in the figure. Looking at figure 3.6 at a glance, however, one might think that five diffusion components are necessary to represent the dataset, since the NRE drops to zero only after the inclusion of five components. While the plateau might alert one that this is not the case, it could be possible that in practical examples, feature obscuration occurs, but there is no clear plateau.

Figure 3.5: The first five diffusion components of a narrow Swiss roll (length 90, height 20). The horizontal axis always represents ψ_1 , the vertical axis represents the higher order components ψ_2, \dots, ψ_5 , going from left to right. The color represents the z -coordinate of the Swiss roll (equation 2.27).

Figure 3.6: Neural reconstruction error of a narrow Swiss roll (width 20, length 90)

This raises a more general question: Not only do we have to investigate *how many* of the first components are needed to describe the data, but also *which* components in the first place. To identify situations like this, I propose a more thorough search of the possible combinations of diffusion components. So far, the neural network always received the first k consecutive diffusion components (ψ_1, \dots, ψ_k) as input. Instead, we can use the following algorithm to determine a possibly better combination of diffusion components:

Search of optimal combination of diffusion components

Parameters:

k_{\max} : Highest order component to consider

T_{\max} : Maximum number of components to consider at the same time

For $T = 0$ to T_{\max} :

For all $j \in \{1, \dots, k_{\max}\} \setminus \{k_1, \dots, k_T\}$:

Calculate NRE $\varepsilon_{T;j}$ of components $(\psi_{k_1}, \dots, \psi_{k_T}, \psi_j)$

Set $k_{T+1} = \arg \min_j \varepsilon_{T;j}$

Output: indices of the optimal components $(k_1, \dots, k_{T_{\max}})$

So, in the first step, the NREs for the components $(\psi_1), (\psi_2), \dots, (\psi_{k_{\max}})$ are calculated separately, and the first optimal component k_1 is set to the one with the lowest reconstruction error. In the subsequent steps, all the components which have previously been considered optimal are retained, and a search is performed to find the next best component to add. The result is the set of components $(\psi_{k_1}, \dots, \psi_{k_{T_{\max}}})$. To interpret the results, one can then plot the NRE in terms of the number of components that are included out of this set and compare it to the version where only consecutive components are considered.

Recall that the training of a neural network, and therefore the calculation of a single NRE, takes a few minutes on an ordinary laptop. It is therefore not feasible to search all possible combinations of diffusion components, hence the greedy algorithm. In principle, it could therefore happen that there are combinations of diffusion components that achieve lower NREs but are not found by this algorithm. At least in the case where some diffusion components are functions of earlier components, however, this concern is no factor. It is also not feasible to include all components in the search, since there are as many diffusion components as data points. We therefore need the parameter k_{\max} for the cutoff after which no more components are considered. This means that we still assume that components with small eigenvalues are irrelevant; since these represent very fast decaying relaxation modes, this assumption should hold.

To illustrate this search, it is applied to the narrow Swiss roll. The result, along with an illustration of the intermediate steps, can be seen in figure 3.7 on the next page. In figures 3.7a-3.7c, we can see how, at every step, the search adds the next diffusion component that minimizes the reconstruction error. Figure 3.7d shows the result, showing clearly that two diffusion components (namely the first and the fifth) are sufficient to describe the dataset with very high accuracy.

(a) Round 1: Searching for the initial diffusion component with the lowest NRE identifies ψ_1 as the optimal choice ($k_1 = 1$).

(b) Round 2: Given ψ_1 as the first diffusion component, the next component to add is determined as ψ_5 ($k_2 = 5$).

(c) Round 3: Given (ψ_1, ψ_5) as the first two diffusion components, the next component to add would be ψ_2 , although one can see there is little difference between components ψ_2, ψ_3 and ψ_4 .

(d) Result: NRE as a function of the number of diffusion components. The components are added in the order $(1, 5, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7)$, determined by the search.

Figure 3.7: Step-by-step illustration of the algorithm to find optimal diffusion components for reconstruction on the example of the narrow Swiss roll. In this case, $k_{\max} = T_{\max} = 7$. Only the first three steps are shown, alongside the final result.

4 The Neural Reconstruction Error in Practice

So far, the Neural Reconstruction Error has been illustrated on the example of the Swiss roll, an artificial dataset with ideal conditions for a nonlinear dimensionality reduction algorithm like the diffusion map. This has shown that in principle, the NRE is suitable as a quality measure for an embedding, conforming well to our expectations of what it means for an embedding to be high-quality. It can also be used to identify relevant diffusion components. Of course, the Swiss roll is a highly idealized example, and we can expect any analysis on real-life data to behave differently. The goal of this chapter is therefore to verify if the NRE is also meaningful when applied to dimensionality reductions of less artificial datasets. This will test on one hand the usefulness of the NRE as a quality measure. At the same time, we will see how it can be used to gain insight into a dataset.

For this purpose, I will use three different datasets from physics and social science. In all three cases, the NRE is illustrated by applying it to the diffusion map of the dataset. This is compared to the PCA of the same dataset, demonstrating how the NRE can also be used to compare the outcomes of different dimensionality reduction techniques. The datasets are chosen to be very diverse in terms of their properties, such as the number of features and the dimensionality and geometry of the data manifold. At the same time, they are all related to applications where manifold learning has been used in current research, showcasing the diverse applications of the diffusion map.

First, in section 4.1, I consider a dataset of spin configurations in the Ising model. It is very high-dimensional, yet we know that there is a single parameter, the magnetization, which is very important to describing the data. We will see if the diffusion map identifies it as the most important quantity and how this is reflected in the NRE. The fact that the Ising model is well known and understood will help us in interpreting the results.

Next, in section 4.2, the dataset will also come from a physical simulation. This time, the system consists of chaotically behaving coupled oscillators, with the dataset representing the phase space coordinates of the system as it evolves in time. In this example, the manifold hypothesis is clearly fulfilled, thanks to a number of conserved quantities which constrict the system to a submanifold in phase space. This gives dimensionality reduction a very physical interpretation. In contrast to the Ising model, the dataset is relatively low-dimensional, but introduces significant nonlinearities.

Finally, in section 4.3, we will encounter an example of a high-dimensional dataset from the social sciences, the V-Dem dataset. In contrast to the other two examples, it comes from empirical observations. We can therefore expect the data to be very noisy. The dataset is also heterogeneous, featuring different types of variables, including some partially discrete ones.

4.1 Ising Model

The first dataset, which we will examine in this section, is drawn from solid state physics, a potentially interesting field for applications of the diffusion map. Dimensionality reduction techniques [55] including the diffusion map [56] have already been used to study phase transitions in solid states. In this section, we shall consider the classic example of the ferromagnetic Ising model on a two-dimensional lattice [57]. This lets us test the NRE on a system that is already well-studied and where we have a good idea of what to expect.

System

The model consists of p spins $\sigma_i \in \{-1, +1\}$, each located at a site i of a two-dimensional lattice. They are coupled by the Hamiltonian

$$H = - \sum_{i \sim j} \sigma_i \sigma_j, \quad (4.1)$$

where the sum is over all pairs of nearest neighbor sites. The system therefore favors an alignment of neighboring spins. The order parameter and central quantity of the Ising model is the magnetization $m = \frac{1}{p} \sum_i \sigma_i$. It is well known [57] that the Ising model has two phases, separated by a critical point at $T_c \approx 2.27$. In the ferromagnetic phase at $T < T_c$, the tendency to align neighboring spins prevails, leading to a non-zero magnetization. The system breaks the symmetry of the Hamiltonian, taking on a state of either positive or negative magnetization. In the paramagnetic phase at $T > T_c$, thermal disorder prevails, leading to a vanishing magnetization.

Methods

Spin configurations are sampled from the equilibrium distribution of a 30×30 lattice with periodic boundary conditions. The Metropolis-Hastings algorithm is used with an implementation based on [58]. The full code and data are available in [30]. To ensure that samples are independent and drawn from the equilibrium distribution, the model is initialized separately for every sample and at least 1000 Monte Carlo steps are taken before sampling. Three different temperatures are used: $T = 2$ (ferromagnetic phase), $T = 3$ (paramagnetic phase), $T = T_c$ (critical point). For each temperature, a dataset is compiled by sampling 12,000 configurations and treating the spins of the configuration as entries of a $p = 900$ -dimensional vector. In total, we therefore have three datasets of dimension 900 with 12,000 observations each, to which we can apply dimensionality reduction.

Results

Figure 4.1 shows the PCA and the diffusion map of the datasets. The first two principal or diffusion components are shown. In every plot, the color represents the magnetization of

Figure 4.1: PCA and diffusion map of configurations of the Ising model at three different temperatures: $T = 2$ (ferromagnetic phase, left), $T = 2.27$ (critical point, middle), $T = 3$ (paramagnetic phase, right). The configurations are colored according to their magnetization. Note that the scales vary by subplot.

the configuration. In all cases, the first principal or diffusion component corresponds to the magnetization. In the case of PCA, this can be deduced from the weights of the first principal component, which are all nearly equal, which amounts to taking the average of all spins. The diffusion map is nonparametric, so that the diffusion components do not have a functional dependency on the variables of the original dataset. However, we can still conclude that ψ_1 corresponds to the magnetization by correlating the two. In this case, this is already quite apparent from the plots. It therefore appears that the magnetization is the most important scalar quantity to describe a spin configuration, just as we would intuitively expect.

In the ferromagnetic phase, both in PCA and diffusion map, two clusters can be clearly identified, which correspond to the two possible signs of the magnetization. No such clusters can be seen in the paramagnetic phase, where the magnetization is centered around zero. At the critical temperature, we note that due to the small system size, we cannot actually observe any critical phenomena. Instead, in the finite system, the

transition between the ferromagnetic and paramagnetic cases is smooth. For instance, there is non-zero magnetization, whereas in the thermodynamic limit, the magnetization at the critical point is zero. What we therefore observe is just an intermediate case, where the magnetization still follows a bimodal distribution, like in the ferromagnetic phase, which is however much smoother. This can be clearly seen in the PCA. The first two diffusion components of the dataset at the critical temperature show the parabola which is characteristic for the diffusion map.

Figure 4.2 now shows the NRE of the diffusion map depending on the number of included components. The hyperparameters used for training are found in table A.3 in the appendix. Shown alongside for comparison is the unexplained variance of the PCA. We can see that the values lie very close together, which seems to indicate that both methods capture the same amount of information. The reason for this could be that there are no nonlinearities in the data which would cause the diffusion map to perform better than PCA. This seems plausible, since there is no reason to assume that the data lie on a nonlinear submanifold. Indeed, the magnetization is just a linear combination of all spins. We also note that there is almost no change in reconstruction error after the first component. Apparently, apart from the magnetization, PCA and the diffusion map can not identify another scalar quantity that adds a lot of information about the configurations. The NRE of the first diffusion component varies, being the smallest in the ferromagnetic case, and almost one in the paramagnetic case. This can be explained by the fact that the first component contains the information about the magnetization. In the ferromagnetic phase, once the magnetization is known, there is little variance: Most of the spins are aligned in the direction given by the magnetization and thus easy to reconstruct. In the paramagnetic phase on the other hand, the magnetization is always close to zero, and gives us little information about the orientation of individual spins.

In fact, we can use this to verify the NRE quantitatively, by calculating analytically what we expect the reconstruction error to be: Since the first diffusion component gives us the information about the magnetization $m = \frac{1}{p} \sum_i \sigma_i$ of any configuration, but no information

Figure 4.2: Reconstruction errors of the Ising configurations at the three different temperatures. Red: NRE of the diffusion map. Blue: Unexplained variance of PCA

about how it is distributed, the neural network can minimize the reconstruction error by guessing the magnetization for every lattice site:

$$\tilde{\sigma}_i = m = \frac{1}{p} \sum_i \sigma_i \quad \forall i, \quad (4.2)$$

where the tilde denotes the estimate of the network and the index i the lattice site. Assuming this reconstruction, the reconstruction error ε is just the variance of spins within one configuration. We can calculate it approximately in mean field theory, where we can assume that all spins are distributed independently:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon &= \frac{1}{p} \sum_i \langle (\sigma_i - \tilde{\sigma}_i)^2 \rangle &= \langle (\sigma_i - m)^2 \rangle \\ &= \langle \sigma_i^2 \rangle - 2 \langle \sigma_i m \rangle + \langle m^2 \rangle &= 1 - 2m^2 + m^2 \\ &= 1 - m^2, \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where $\langle \cdot \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average.

Figure 4.3 shows the prediction from equation 4.3 for the three temperatures that were used and compares it to the empirical NRE given only the first diffusion component. m in this case is taken as the mean magnetization at the given temperature, as taken empirically from the samples. The two values clearly agree very well. This confirms that the NRE works as intended, in this case with ψ_1 acting as a proxy for the magnetization. It also shows that in this case, the tuning of the neural network worked sufficiently well. The network is clearly able to find the optimal reconstruction, reinforcing our confidence in the NRE. This is also an example of how the NRE can be interpreted quantitatively, as opposed to other quality metrics for dimensionality reduction methods. The NRE also reveals that on the Ising model dataset, the diffusion map performs equally well as PCA. This is likely due to the nature of the data, which does not lie on a nonlinear manifold.

Figure 4.3: NRE from just the first diffusion component for Ising configurations at different temperatures (blue triangles). This is compared to the theoretical prediction from equation 4.3 (red circles).

4.2 FPUT System

For an example of a dataset that features strong nonlinearities, let us turn to a dynamical system, the Fermi-Pasta-Ulam-Tsingou (FPUT) system.¹ Thanks to a number of conservation laws, the system only discovers a lower-dimensional submanifold of its phase space, giving a physical meaning to the manifold hypothesis. We can therefore use dimensionality reduction techniques to describe this manifold. In this case, we know the intrinsic dimensionality of the invariant manifold, giving us a ground truth for our analysis. For more complex systems, one could try to use manifold learning techniques to examine the phase space and perhaps even discover conservation laws empirically. One such an approach has been put forward by Liu and Tegmark [60].

System

The FPUT α -system [61] consists of a string of N one-dimensional oscillators with positions x_i and momenta p_i . The oscillators have harmonic and cubic couplings to their nearest neighbors:

$$H = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \frac{p_i^2}{2m} + \frac{1}{2}(x_{i+1} - x_i)^2 + \frac{\alpha}{3}(x_{i+1} - x_i)^3 \quad (4.4)$$

As opposed to the original paper, which had fixed boundary conditions, I use periodic boundary conditions in this thesis. The oscillators x_N and x_0 are therefore identified with each other. The phase space of the system is $2N$ -dimensional. However, there are three conserved quantities: The energy H is conserved, as is the total momentum $P = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} p_i$, thanks to the periodic boundary conditions. By choosing the initial conditions such that $P = 0$, the center of mass $X = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} x_i$ is also conserved, and we choose $X = 0$. These conserved quantities restrict the phase space coordinates of the same simulation to a $(2N - 3)$ -dimensional invariant manifold \mathcal{M} :

$$\mathcal{M} = \{(x, p) \in \mathbb{R}^{2N} : H(x, p) = E_0, P(p) = 0, X(x) = 0\} \quad (4.5)$$

The idea is now to run a numerical simulation of the FPUT system for a long time and sample phase space coordinates of the system at different times. We can then use the diffusion map to identify \mathcal{M} . For the simulations, I used $N = 3$, leading to a three-dimensional invariant manifold. Beyond the dimensionality, we can describe the topology of \mathcal{M} : The momentum and center of mass are linear combinations of the phase space coordinates. \mathcal{M} therefore lies in a four-dimensional linear subspace of \mathbb{R}^6 . We can take this into account by simply substituting $x_0 = -x_1 - x_2$ and $p_0 = -p_1 - p_2$ in equation 4.4. The conservation of energy then further restricts the system to the three-dimensional submanifold \mathcal{M} , whose topology we can understand as follows: From equation 4.4, it is clear that H has a local minimum at the origin $(x, p) = 0$. Close to the origin, the quadratic terms dominate over the cubic term governed by α . For small energy E , the

¹Originally known as the Fermi-Pasta-Ulam system, without credit to Mary Tsingou, see Dauxois [59]

latter can therefore be neglected, so that the equipotential surface $\{H = E\}$ has a connected component close to the origin that is homeomorphic to the 3-sphere S^3 . The topology of the equipotential surface only changes at critical points of H . Apart from the minimum at the origin, the only critical points of the Hamiltonian are saddle points at $E = \frac{1}{\alpha^2}$.² This corresponds to the point where the repulsive part of the cubic interactions allows for runaway solutions. Therefore, for suitable initial conditions with $E < \frac{1}{\alpha^2}$, the system is restricted to a manifold in phase space which is homeomorphic to S^3 .

It is not clear a priori if the system will explore all of M , or if it is further restricted to a subset of possibly lower dimensionality. For that, it would be useful to know if the system behaves ergodically. Even though initially, the FPUT system became famous for its, at the time unexpected, ergodicity breaking, it is now known that in many regimes, the FPUT system exhibits chaotic behavior and energy equipartition, suggesting ergodicity. Casetti et al. [62] numerically studied the model with fixed boundary conditions and chain lengths $N = 8..64$. They conclude statistical mechanics behavior above a threshold energy of $E_c \sim \frac{1}{N}$. Enz et al. [63] analytically determined bounds for the threshold energy E_c . For the FPUT α -model with periodic boundary conditions, they came up with N -independent bounds of $\frac{1}{4\alpha^2} \leq E_c \leq \frac{1}{2\alpha^2}$.

From the available literature, we can therefore conclude that the following factors favor ergodicity: a large system size N , strong nonlinearity α and high energy E . For that reason, I chose a large value of $\alpha = 3$ and initial conditions with an energy just below $\frac{1}{\alpha^2}$, above which runaway solutions would be possible. Only the large N is not fulfilled. I decided to use $N = 3$ so that the dimensionality of M would be manageable. If it was too high, it would be difficult for any dimensionality reduction algorithm to identify the manifold due to the curse of dimensionality. Most literature focuses on the high- N limit, so we cannot make strong statements about the ergodicity of the system, but it is reasonable to assume that the trajectory explores at least a large, three-dimensional, subset of the available manifold.

Methods

The time evolution of the FPUT system is simulated by integrating the corresponding system of first order differential equations. Since this does not guarantee the known conservation laws, high precision is needed to achieve the conservation to within good accuracy. The SciPy [64] implementation of an 8th order Runge-Kutta method is therefore used, with low tolerances. The details of this simulation, such as the initial conditions used, are shown in table 4.1 on the following page. We can confirm that the precision is sufficient by checking the conserved quantities for any drift. In the resulting simulation, any deviations in conserved quantities are very small. The maximal deviation of the energy from its initial value is less than $1.1e-8$ (relative deviation $<9.7e-8$). The total momentum and center of mass deviate by less than $1.4e-14$ and $2.6e-11$, respectively.

²The derivation for this can be found in the repository [30]: https://github.com/nebnola/masterthesis/blob/main/fput/fput_topology.ipynb

Table 4.1: Technical details of the simulation of the FPUT system

System parameters	$N = 3, m = 1, \alpha = 3$
Initial conditions	$(x_1, p_1, x_2, p_2, x_3, p_3) = (0.19, 0.05, -0.06, 0.01, -0.13, -0.06)$
Energy	$E \approx 0.1048$
Integration interval	$(0, 20000)$
Samples	12000 samples of phase space coordinates at random times
Integration method	8th order Runge-Kutta method
Tolerances	relative tolerance: 1e-10, absolute tolerance: 1e-12

The resulting time evolution is then sampled at 12,000 randomly selected time points, leading to a six-dimensional dataset with 12,000 data points. I then calculate the diffusion map (parameters: $\varepsilon = 10, \alpha = 1$) of the standardized dataset and subsequently calculate the NREs. The hyperparameters used for training are found in table A.4 in the appendix.

Results

Figure 4.4a shows the NREs of the diffusion map and PCA of the FPUT dataset. The unexplained variance of PCA is also shown for comparison. We can see that the behavior of both dimensionality reduction methods is very similar: a continuous reduction of the reconstruction error until it reaches zero at four components. Before that, the diffusion map performs only slightly better than PCA. Even though the data manifold is three-dimensional, the diffusion map apparently needs four diffusion components to describe the dataset. This is actually not surprising, since \mathcal{M} is homeomorphic to S^3 . The diffusion map is built to preserve local neighborhoods, and there exists no mapping $S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ that does not rip some neighborhoods apart. At least four dimensions are therefore needed to embed \mathcal{M} . A lower-dimensional example of the same idea has been mentioned by Coifman and Lafon [13]: They consider a closed curve in \mathbb{R}^3 , which is mapped to a circle in the first two diffusion components. Two diffusion components are therefore needed to describe a one-dimensional manifold in that example. PCA is also able to parametrize the dataset with four components, since \mathcal{M} lies on a four-dimensional linear subspace of \mathbb{R}^6 , hence the similar performance of PCA and diffusion map. However, the three-dimensionality of the manifold can still be revealed by only considering a subset of the entire manifold.

In a subsequent experiment, let us consider a subset of the manifold by choosing a point $x_0 \in \mathcal{M}$ at random and only including points x within a given radius of x_0 :

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{neigh}} = \{x \in \mathcal{M} : \|x - x_0\| < 4\} \quad (4.6)$$

This covers approximately half of the entire manifold \mathcal{M} , introducing a boundary and making sure that this time, $\mathcal{M}_{\text{neigh}}$ is homeomorphic to a compact subset of \mathbb{R}^3 . It should therefore be possible to parametrize the manifold accurately with just three diffusion components. In order to ensure that there are still enough points for the diffusion map, a larger amount of points (50,000) is first sampled from \mathcal{M} by simulating the FPUT system

Figure 4.4: Reconstruction error of the diffusion map of the FPUT dataset, compared with PCA. “PCA (residual variance)” refers to the unexplained variance of PCA. “PCA (DNN)” refers to the Neural Reconstruction Error of PCA.

for a longer time. The restriction to $\mathcal{M}_{\text{neigh}}$ then contains 27,907 points. Of those points, 12,000 are chosen at random, so that the results of the diffusion map would be comparable to the previous experiment using the entire manifold. On the resulting dataset, I perform the same analysis as previously.

The results are shown in figure 4.4b. This time we can see clearly that the reconstruction error goes to almost zero once at least three diffusion components are included. This is in comparison to PCA, which still shows a residual variance of 0.16 for the first three principal components. However, when calculating the NRE of the PCA, the resulting error is almost as low as that of the diffusion map (0.030 instead of 0.015). This is an example of the difference between the residual variance and the Neural Reconstruction Error of PCA. In this case, the manifold $\mathcal{M}_{\text{neigh}}$ is clearly nonlinear; however, it can still be well represented by three principal components if we allow the reconstruction to be nonlinear.

The example of the FPUT dataset confirms the utility of the NRE to evaluate the quality of a dimensionality reduction. The results are consistent with what we know about the data manifold from reasoning about its geometry. This example also shows how the NRE can be used to discover the dimensionality and the topology of the data manifold, making it also a tool for data exploration.

4.3 V-Dem Dataset

Finally, to show an example where the diffusion map is applied to a high-dimensional social science dataset, let us turn to a large democracy dataset, the V-Dem dataset [65].

Dataset

The V-Dem (Varieties of Democracy) project sets out to measure different aspects of democracy in a disaggregated way. This is borne out of the idea that democracy is a multifaceted concept for which there is no single, universally accepted definition. This sets it apart from older democracy indices such as the Polity and Freedom House indices with their unidimensional rankings [66]. V-Dem has five democracy indices, representing five key principles of democracy: electoral, liberal, participatory and egalitarian – the titular *Varieties of Democracy* [67]. They are calculated in multiple levels of aggregation: In version 12, used in this thesis, there are 483 *indicators*, coded by country experts and research assistants, which measure a rather narrow feature (e.g. v2e1embaut – election management body autonomy). The indicators are aggregated into 21 *mid-level indices* (e.g. v2xe1_frefair – Clean elections index) and the five *high-level indices* [68]. Among these, the electoral democracy index (EDI, identified as v2x_polyarchy in the dataset) takes on a central role, since the V-Dem authors consider that there can be no democracy without elections [67]. I use the country-year dataset, where the indicators and indices are provided for every year and country for which there is coverage; a country-date version is also available. Most independent countries since 1900 are covered. The availability of disaggregated data, data coverage and transparency have earned V-Dem a reputation as one of the highest-quality datasets of democracy measures [66].

The disaggregated nature of the dataset offers a lot of opportunity to study democracy as a multi-faceted concept. However, this very strength also poses the same challenges as high-dimensional data always does: It is not possible to visualize the full dataset appropriately, and any analysis suffers from the curse of dimensionality. It is therefore desirable to apply dimensionality reduction to the dataset. For that reason, PCA [69] and the diffusion map [22] have already been applied to a subset of the V-Dem dataset.

Methods

In the following, the setup from Pirker-Díaz et al. [22] is reproduced by calculating the diffusion map of a subset of the V-Dem dataset. The NRE is then calculated in order to evaluate the quality of the diffusion map. Only a subset of the V-Dem dataset, which pertains to the EDI, is used. In V-Dem, the EDI is calculated from five mid-level indices: the “freedom of expression and alternative sources of information” (v2x_freexp_altinf), freedom of association (v2x_frassoc_thick), suffrage (v2x_suffr), clean elections (v2xe1_frfair) and elected officials (v2x_elecoff) indices. The dataset used here contains the suffrage and elected officials indices and the 23 indicators that make up the other three indices. The underlying indicators are used instead of the indices in order to not rely on the a priori assumptions behind the composition of the indices; instead, we want to keep the

high dimensionality of the dataset, with the diffusion map identifying relevant features. However, it was decided to use the elected officials index instead of the indicators that make it up, since most of those indicators are binary and are by themselves not very informative about the state of a democracy (for instance whether the head of state is the same as the head of government). In the case of the suffrage index, the mid-level index is the same as the indicator, measuring simply the proportion of the adult population that is allowed to vote. A complete list of the variables included in the dataset can be found in table A.1 in the appendix.

All observations with complete data since 1900 are included in the sample; this covers 174 different countries. Since data pertaining to election quality is only available for election years, it is interpolated by repeating the values from the last election year, for up to four years. This means that countries which do not hold elections are not included in the sample. The resulting dataset consists of 12296 observations for 25 variables ($p = 25, N = 12296$), one observation corresponding to one country-year. I calculate the diffusion map of the dataset with the same parameters as in Pirker-Díaz et al. [22] for consistency ($\varepsilon = 10, \alpha = \frac{1}{2}, 100$ nearest neighbors). The components are standardized to a mean of zero and standard deviation of one before applying the diffusion map.

4.3.1 Results

The first three diffusion components are shown in figure 4.5. ψ_1 corresponds very well to the EDI, confirming that the latter is the most important scalar quantity to describe the dataset. The first two components are similar to the parabola that is characteristic for the diffusion map of one-dimensional manifolds, suggesting that ψ_2 does not capture a lot of information that is independent from ψ_1 . Looking at subfigure 4.5b, we can see that ψ_3 also shows some similarity to the third-order polynomial that would be expected from a one-dimensional manifold. However, there is some more deviation, notably, an additional structure at $\psi_1 \in [0, 1]$, which appears to “split off” from the rest of the dataset. For a more detailed discussion of this diffusion map, refer to Pirker-Díaz et al. [22].

Crucially for this thesis, only the first three diffusion components are shown, just like in the original paper [22]. Without a measure for the relevance of diffusion components, there is no concrete justification for this choice, and it is not clear how much and what information is lost by omitting the subsequent components. The spectrum (figure 4.6) is as uninformative as usual. Instead, I calculate the NRE for this diffusion map; the hyperparameters for the training of the decoders are, as always, listed in the appendix, in table A.5.

The resulting NRE is shown in figure 4.7 as a function of the number of included diffusion components. For comparison, the unexplained variance and the NRE of the PCA are also included. For comparing the quality of the diffusion map and PCA fairly, the NRE should be used for both methods. We can see that the reconstruction errors of the diffusion map and PCA are very similar. The NREs using just the first component are 0.27 and 0.29, respectively. One could say that for the purposes of reconstruction, both methods have an accuracy of more than 70%. When additionally, the second component is included, the reconstruction errors drop to 0.17 and 0.19, respectively. With each further added component, there is less improvement to the reconstruction error. After about the seventh diffusion component, the NRE all but stops decreasing. For few components, the diffusion map seems to slightly outperform PCA, before being overtaken; PCA then achieves the lower NRE. The former effect is small in magnitude, while the latter is quite pronounced (NRE for the first ten components: 0.072 (diffusion map) vs 0.025 (PCA)). It is difficult to say whether this is because the higher-order diffusion components genuinely do not contain new information, or if they do, but it becomes harder for the network to learn. Of course, in the case of PCA, the neural network that learns the reconstruction only has to approximate a function which is close to a linear map, for which the structure of the neural network is very well adapted. The diffusion components on the other hand are not orthogonal to each other, and the relationship between the original data and the embedding is more complex.

(a) The first two components

(b) Components ψ_1 and ψ_3

Figure 4.5: Diffusion map of the V-Dem dataset: first three components. The color corresponds to the electoral democracy index in the V-Dem dataset. The same embedding can be found in Pirker-Díaz et al. [22].

Figure 4.6: Spectrum λ^t of the diffusion map of the V-Dem dataset for a few different values of t . As in the case of the Swiss roll, it is of not much use when trying to decide how many diffusion components to include in practice.

Figure 4.7: Comparison of different kinds of reconstruction errors for dimensionality reductions of the V-Dem dataset. Red: NRE of the diffusion map. Green: NRE of PCA. Blue: unexplained variance of PCA.

4.3.2 Reconstruction Error by Variable

The Neural Reconstruction Error can also be calculated separately for each variable of the input dataset. This gives a more granular picture and can be used to gain further insight into the data. The partial NRE for the j th component of the input dataset is calculated by considering only the j th variable instead of the entire dataset in equation 3.6:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{part},j} = \left\langle \left\| \hat{\Psi}_j^{-1}(\Psi(\mathbf{x})) - x_{.j} \right\|^2 \right\rangle = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left\| \hat{\Psi}_j^{-1}(\Psi(x_i)) - x_{ij} \right\|^2. \quad (4.7)$$

Here, x_{ij} refers to the value of the j th observable at data point i . The total NRE is of course just the mean of all partial NREs. To demonstrate the utility of this type of analysis, figure 4.8 shows the partial NREs for the diffusion map of the V-Dem dataset. We can see markedly different behavior for the different variables, which we distinguish in three groups:

The indicators that make up the indices for freedom of expression and freedom of association can be reconstructed with relatively high accuracy even from just one diffusion component (all reconstruction errors < 0.22 , see top panel). There is a moderate, gradual improvement with a higher number of components.

Most of the indicators that make up the clean elections index have a much higher NRE when only few dimensions are included (see middle panel in figure 4.8). At one included component, only two of these indicators (`v2e1embaut` and `v2e1frfair`) have an NRE of less than 0.22. The electoral indicator with the highest NRE from one diffusion component is `v2e1peace`, with an NRE of 0.56. It measures violence during elections by non-government parties. All of these indicators show a gradual decrease of their NRE when more diffusion components are included. This agrees well with the findings from the PCA of the V-Dem dataset by Wiesner et al. [69]. They found that there is a trade-off between election capability (measured by the indicators that make up the clean elections index) and civil liberties (measured by the indices pertaining to freedom of association and expression). While civil liberties generally go hand in hand with a high EDI, the same cannot be said for election capability. Since ψ_1 is very closely related to the EDI, the high NRE when using just ψ_1 as input can be interpreted to mean that the EDI is not a reliable predictor for election capability. In fact, many autocratic regimes which run tightly controlled elections score high on indicators such as capacity of the election management body or absence of violence during elections.

Finally, the elected officials and suffrage indices show a completely different behavior. Their NRE is shown in the bottom panel of figure 4.8. It is very high at only one diffusion component and decreases rapidly once the next one or two components are included. For the first three diffusion components, the NREs for the suffrage and elected officials indices are only 0.053 and 0.036, respectively, much less than for any other variable. This is most likely because both of these indices are semi-discrete, typically taking one of only a few values. The elected officials index (`v2x_e1ecoff`) measures whether the chief executive and the legislature are legitimized through popular elections, either directly or indirectly. It uses a minimal definition, including also sham elections [68]. This is why in the year 2021, 80% of included countries score exactly 1 on this index. In the entire

Figure 4.8: Per-Variable NRE for the diffusion map of the V-Dem dataset. The variables are grouped into three categories. Upper panel: indicators pertaining to freedom of expression and freedom of association. Middle panel: indicators pertaining to clean elections. Bottom panel: the two indices `v2x_elecoeff` and `v2x_suffr`, which are both semi-discrete

dataset, around 87% of all observations have a value of either 0 or 1. The suffrage index (`v2x_suffr`) behaves similarly. In 84% of the observations, it takes on one of only two values: 1 (universal suffrage) or 0.5 (usually male-only suffrage). Other small values are also possible, e.g. when some ethnic groups are excluded from the vote. These semi-discrete indices do not appear to strongly factor into ψ_1 . However, it appears that the discrete variables have a disproportionately large effect on the diffusion components ψ_2 and ψ_3 . The diffusion map space is therefore neatly split into regions where these variables take on different values, making the reconstruction easy to learn for the neural network. This is in line with the findings by Beier [27] that discrete variables can turn out to be problematic for the diffusion map, which is not tailored to them.

This type of analysis again shows how the NRE can be used as a tool for data exploration. In this case, it allows us to analyze the different variables of the dataset and their relationships. This way, the NRE can provide a valuable starting point for further data analysis.

4.3.3 Combinations of Nonconsecutive Diffusion Components

The search of diffusion components, laid out in section 3.8, is applied on the V-Dem dataset in order to test it on a real-life example. This allows us to see if feature obscuration is of concern for the diffusion map of the V-Dem dataset. The search is illustrated in figure 4.9. In every round except for the first, training was repeated several times to account for noise due to the random initialization of the neural network parameters. As expected, it turns out that the first diffusion component, ψ_1 , is optimal for reconstructing the dataset from just one component. When searching for the second component, it turns out that (ψ_1, ψ_4) performs slightly better than (ψ_1, ψ_2) , indicating that ψ_4 might offer more information independent from ψ_1 than ψ_2 does. This is somewhat similar to the feature obscuration we saw in the narrow Swiss roll; however, the effect is much smaller. Compared to the NRE of 0.27 with just ψ_1 , the NREs for the components (ψ_1, ψ_2) and (ψ_1, ψ_4) are quite similar (0.17 vs 0.15 on average). This is a rather different situation from the feature obscuration we could see in the Swiss roll, where adding the second diffusion component did not improve the reconstruction error at all. In fact, with the V-Dem dataset, this seems to hold at all levels of the search, except for the first. It seems not to matter as much *which* components are used for the reconstruction, rather *how many* components are used. This is even more so the case in the later rounds of the search. In many cases, the differences in NRE between different sets of components are smaller than the differences between NREs of the same components due to noise. This complicates the search and the decision which components to retain. For instance, in the search for the third diffusion component to include in the mapping (figure 4.9c), I decided to use ψ_{11} , even though it did not strictly achieve the lowest NRE overall. This is because the noise was relatively small for that set of components and because it seemed prudent to avoid very high-order components if possible. Other choices would of course also be justifiable in this case.

Based on the results of the search, I decided to use diffusion components in the order (1, 4, 11, 15). I refrained from continuing the search for even more components, because the results were too noisy to draw meaningful conclusions. The NRE using this ordering is shown in figure 4.10 on page 54, compared with the NRE in the conventional order. The NRE of the PCA is also shown for further comparison. Even though the improvements over taking diffusion components in order are rather small at each step, they slowly add up. The NRE for the four components (1, 4, 11, 15) deemed “optimal” is 0.07, compared to the 0.1 of the first four diffusion components. This shows that the proposed method can find mappings that are higher-quality than the conventional diffusion map in the sense of the reconstruction error.

Overall, it seems that the diffusion map of the V-Dem dataset shows properties similar to feature obscuration, where some higher-order diffusion components can add more information than lower-order components. However, the picture is much less clear than in the synthetic example of the narrow Swiss roll. In particular, the effect size is much smaller. It seems that all considered mappings that include the same number of components have very similar NREs, as long as the first diffusion component is included. It is not clear why this is the case. In any case, the proposed search method can help identify combinations of

(a) Round 1: Unsurprisingly, ψ_1 is clearly the diffusion component that, on its own, is best suited to describe the dataset

(b) Round 2: Given ψ_1 as the first diffusion component, the next best component is not ψ_2 , but ψ_4 .

(c) Round 3: The differences in NRE between different sets of components start to become very small, so that noise becomes very relevant.

(d) Round 4

Figure 4.9: Search for optimal diffusion components to encode the V-Dem dataset. Most of the runs were repeated several times with the same parameters to account for noise. They are marked separately in the plots, leading to multiple values for the same set of components. In all cases, the diffusion components up to ψ_{25} have been searched; for a readable presentation, some of the NREs for higher-order components have been truncated. Note also the different scales in each plot.

Figure 4.10: Comparison of NRE between optimal nonconsecutive diffusion components (green) and the conventional consecutive components (red). The components considered for the nonconsecutive case are (1, 4, 11, 15). When multiple runs were performed, the mean is shown. For further comparison, the NRE of PCA is also shown (blue).

diffusion components that might not have been considered otherwise. It is not necessary to pick exactly those components which offer the absolute lowest reconstruction error. The example of the V-Dem dataset shows that, given the noise, this might not even be possible without expending significant resources. One might of course use higher-capacity neural networks or repeat the training a large number of times until the errors are small enough to compare the NREs. However, given the small differences in reconstruction error, this is arguably not worth the effort. Rather, the search of diffusion components can be seen as a tool to help data practitioners identify which diffusion components to consider for further analysis. While it is unfeasible to manually consider a myriad of different combinations of diffusion components, this search can identify candidates for components which may be of interest.

To give an example of the type of analysis that might follow after identifying such candidates, consider the two diffusion components of the V-Dem dataset identified as optimal by this search: ψ_1 and ψ_4 . Normally, one might not even think to consider ψ_4 ; in many applications, not more than the first two or three diffusion components are even considered. In figure 4.11a, these diffusion components are shown.

In order to find out why the reconstruction error is smaller for components (ψ_1, ψ_4) as opposed to components (ψ_1, ψ_2) , we can turn to the partial reconstruction errors to find out which variables contribute most to this difference. It turns out that there is a large difference in the elected officials index, with a partial NRE of 0.09 vs 0.33. Coloring the plot by that index shows why that is: The data points with high vs low elected officials index are well separated in the diffusion map space spanned by the first and fourth components (figure 4.11b). If we compare this to the first two components, we can see that they are much more mixed (figure 4.11c). This again highlights the special status of discrete variables and the effect they have on the diffusion map. Of course, if the possible values are well separated in diffusion map space, it is easy for the network to reconstruct a discrete variable, since the regression task essentially turns into a classification task.

(a) The first and fourth diffusion components for the V-Dem dataset.

(b) The same components, colored according to the elected officials index.

(c) For comparison, the first two diffusion components colored according to the elected officials index.

Figure 4.11: Comparing diffusion components 1 and 4 to the first two diffusion components. It appears that the elected officials index is much better captured by the former.

5 Summary and Discussion

This thesis focused on quantifying the quality of the diffusion map for the purposes of dimensionality reduction. While the diffusion map has been applied in a wide range of fields, no consistent treatment of this question has emerged. When it is considered at all, the most widely cited metric is the eigenvalue spectrum of the diffusion map. In this thesis, it is argued that it is unsuitable for this purpose. I therefore proposed the Neural Reconstruction Error (NRE), which extends the well-established concept of the reconstruction error to nonparametric dimensionality reduction methods, where the inverse mapping is not available explicitly. I subsequently applied it to diffusion maps of both synthetic and real-life datasets to test its validity and showcase possible applications. Although this thesis is focused on the diffusion map, the NRE is in fact method-agnostic and can therefore be applied to any dimensionality reduction method.

Interpretation and Properties of the NRE

Thanks to its straightforward definition, the NRE is easy to interpret quantitatively, giving an intuitive indication of how much information is preserved by a dimensionality reduction algorithm. In particular, its definition is consistent with the unexplained variance in PCA, making the two quantities directly comparable. Researchers will therefore find it easy to work with the NRE. For instance, it can help make an informed decision as to how many diffusion components should be used to describe a dataset.

This sets it apart from other existing quality measures for dimensionality reduction methods. In particular, the measures based on the co-ranking framework are difficult to interpret quantitatively. This was demonstrated for one representative, the Local Continuity Meta-Criterion (LCMC), on the example of the Swiss roll. There is also a lot of freedom in defining these rank-based measures, leading to a whole array of metrics with slightly differing definitions. This is in contrast with the reconstruction error, which can only really be defined one way. In order to put the NRE better into context, future work could focus on comparing it to more quality measures, which might include other methods which are based on the co-ranking framework.

The NRE is based solely on the quality of the reconstruction, which is an indicator of how much information from the original dataset is preserved. It can not tell us if the coordinates given by the dimensionality reduction are also useful. In fact, the NRE is insensitive to any distortion that one could apply to the embedding as long as it is bijective. Since no information is lost, undoing the distortion can just be learned by the decoder. The NRE also does not penalize what in the language of the co-ranking framework are called “extrusions”, i.e. pairs of data points which are close together in the original data, but far apart in the embedding. For instance, if a closed loop were to be mapped to an open

line segment by tearing it apart at some point, this would not impede the reconstruction by the neural network. This sets the NRE apart from other quality measures which do penalize distortions. It might also explain some of the difference between the LCMC and the NRE of the Swiss roll. Perhaps the LCMC was influenced by some distortions introduced by the diffusion map, which the NRE could compensate.

It should also be kept in mind that the reconstruction error is always in terms of Euclidean distances in the original data space. Since the data manifold is not known a priori, the reconstruction error cannot be measured in terms of geodesic distances. The NRE, just like the diffusion map, is therefore also sensitive to the relative rescaling of variables in the original dataset.

The fact that the data reconstruction is learned by a neural network allows the NRE to be so flexible and method-agnostic. This comes with the cost that is associated with training a neural network. For one, the runtime is considerably longer in comparison to other methods, making it somewhat less practical. The NRE is also nondeterministic, thanks to the random initialization of the network's parameters. In order to make the NRE more reliable, future work could focus on treating the resulting noise more carefully, for instance by repeating the training multiple times.

The training of the decoders also depends on a large number of hyperparameters. Tuning those hyperparameters is not only time-consuming, it also offers significant researcher degrees of freedom. Care must therefore be taken to ensure that the decoder truly learns the reconstruction as best as possible. Fortunately, it appeared during the numerical experiments that, within a reasonable range, the reconstruction is not very sensitive to small changes to the model hyperparameters. We could also see that the NRE is in line with expectations on the examples of the Swiss roll and the Ising model. For the latter example, we also have a theoretical, quantitative prediction with which the NRE agrees very well. This gives us some confidence that the decoders do in fact learn the reconstruction as intended.

The hyperparameter tuning could be made more systematic by employing techniques such as a grid search or Bayesian optimization. Many other avenues for optimizing the learning process are also possible. For example, the cost function of the decoder could be adapted to respond to different needs. In a dataset with strongly varying sample density, for instance, the reconstruction error could be weighted by the inverse of the local density in order to make sure that the reconstruction is also good in sparse regions. Finally, entirely different machine learning models could be used for the decoder instead of the feedforward network. A comparison between different models could reveal which one is best suited for this purpose, both in terms of speed and finding the optimal reconstruction. The Data Space Reconstruction Error (DSRE) by Kramer [54] can be seen in this light. There, a K-nearest-neighbors regression model is used instead of the feedforward network in this thesis. Future work should focus on comparing the two approaches in practice and perhaps also exploring entirely different models.

Applications of the NRE

The datasets that served as examples in this thesis show some of the fields where the NRE can provide a benefit by measuring the quality of a dimensionality reduction. They also provide examples of how the NRE can give us more insight into specific properties of a dataset.

For instance, it can be used to quantitatively compare different dimensionality reduction techniques on the same dataset. In our case, it revealed that in all three non-artificial datasets, the diffusion map did not perform considerably better than PCA in terms of the NRE. Such comparisons could be made with many more different dimensionality reduction methods. The NRE could even serve as a basis for quantitative surveys of dimensionality reduction methods.

The NRE also allows us to treat an often overlooked property of the diffusion map, called feature obscuration in this thesis. This was demonstrated on the examples of the narrow Swiss roll and the V-Dem dataset. Even though feature obscuration has been known since the introduction of the diffusion map, it is not considered in any practical applications of the diffusion map that I could find. This may be because there is little awareness of this phenomenon, or because it is difficult to identify. With the NRE, it is easy to examine many different combinations of diffusion components and perhaps consider some higher-order diffusion components that may be useful but would otherwise remain overlooked. For instance, on the V-Dem dataset, we saw that the NRE is minimized by using the fourth diffusion component instead of the second. The fourth diffusion component has not been considered so far for this dataset. Of course, the NRE alone does not reveal why that is. Understanding how feature obscuration can happen in real-life datasets would certainly be an interesting avenue for further research into spectral dimensionality reduction.

On the example of the V-Dem dataset, we also saw how the NRE can be used not only as a global quality measure, but also to examine how well individual variables of the input dataset are reconstructed. This can be useful to explore the peculiarities of the dataset at hand. For instance, it showed the particular role that semi-discrete variables play in the diffusion map of the V-Dem dataset.

Other possible applications of the NRE, which were not implemented in this thesis, are conceivable. For instance, it could be examined how the NRE varies between individual data points. This might be of particular interest for datasets which have different intrinsic dimensionalities in different regions of the data space. The NRE could also be used to tune the parameters of the dimensionality reduction technique. In the case of the diffusion map, this would be the kernel width ϵ , which could be tuned by calculating diffusion maps with different values of ϵ and choosing the value that minimizes the reconstruction error.

Conclusion

Given the widespread use of nonparametric dimensionality reduction methods, there is a need to quantify how well they are able to represent a dataset. The Neural Reconstruction

Error proposed in this thesis makes a contribution to this problem, which offers an improvement compared to other methods, especially regarding its interpretability. In the context of the diffusion map in particular, it can help in the choice of diffusion components, an often overlooked aspect of the diffusion map. It can also be used to explore many different aspects of a given embedding and thus provide a starting point for further analyses. The training of the neural networks, in particular the hyperparameter tuning, can be involved, potentially limiting the willingness of researchers to apply it. Future work should therefore focus on making it more accessible, perhaps by eliminating some of the degrees of freedom around the choice of hyperparameters and providing easy-to-use implementations. Potential applications of the Neural Reconstruction Error are plentiful. Some of them have been demonstrated in this thesis, while many remain to be explored in future work.

A Appendix

A.1 Proof of the Diffusion Distance Property

Proofs for the diffusion distance property can be found by Coifman and Lafon [13] and in other sources discussing the diffusion map. The following is a more explicit version which also pays attention to the normalization of the diffusion components.

First, we notice that from equation 2.9 follows a biorthonormality relation for the left and right eigenvectors of M :

$$\langle \phi_i, \psi_j \rangle = \delta_{ij} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

If we write as Φ the matrix whose rows are the left eigenvectors ϕ_i and as Ψ the matrix whose columns are the right eigenvectors ψ_j , it therefore holds that

$$\Phi\Psi = 1 \quad (\text{A.2})$$

We can therefore write M in its eigenbasis:

$$M = \Psi\Lambda\Phi, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $\Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{n-1})$ is the matrix of eigenvalues.

The probability $P_t(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x})$ to jump from point \mathbf{x} to \mathbf{y} in exactly t time steps can be expressed in terms of the transition matrix M as

$$P_t(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{e}_x^T M^t \mathbf{e}_y, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where \mathbf{e}_x denotes the unit vector containing a one in the index corresponding to data point \mathbf{x} . We can now rewrite this in the eigenbasis of M :

$$\begin{aligned} P_t(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbf{e}_x^T \Psi \Lambda^t \Phi \mathbf{e}_y \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \psi_j(\mathbf{x}) \lambda_j^t \phi_j(\mathbf{y}) \\ &= \phi_0(\mathbf{y}) + \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} \psi_j(\mathbf{x}) \lambda_j^t \phi_j(\mathbf{y}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where in the last step, we have used that $\psi_0(\mathbf{x}) = \lambda_0 = 1$. This can be interpreted as the stationary distribution ϕ_0 plus terms that depend on the initial distribution, which decay

as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Substituting this expression into the definition of the diffusion distance (2.14) now yields

$$\begin{aligned}
D_t^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) &= \sum_{z \in X} \frac{1}{\phi_0(z)} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N-1} (\psi_j(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_j(\mathbf{y})) \lambda_j^t \phi_j(z) \right)^2 \\
&= \sum_{j,k=1}^{N-1} \sum_{z \in X} \frac{1}{\phi_0(z)} (\psi_j(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_j(\mathbf{y})) \lambda_j^t \phi_j(z) (\psi_k(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_k(\mathbf{y})) \lambda_k^t \phi_k(z) \quad (\text{A.6}) \\
&= \sum_{j,k=1}^{N-1} (\psi_j(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_j(\mathbf{y})) \lambda_j^t (\psi_k(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_k(\mathbf{y})) \lambda_k^t \sum_{z \in X} \frac{1}{\phi_0(z)} \phi_j(z) \phi_k(z)
\end{aligned}$$

We again apply equation 2.9 and denote by $d(z)$ the diagonal entry of D corresponding to the point z . The sum over z then evaluates to

$$\sum_{z \in X} \frac{1}{\phi_0(z)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{tr}(D)}} \mathbf{v}_j(z) d^{1/2}(z) \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{tr}(D)}} \mathbf{v}_k(z) d^{1/2}(z) \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$= \sum_{z \in X} \frac{d(z)}{\text{tr}(D) \phi_0(z)} v_j(z) v_k(z) \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$= \delta_{jk}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

because of the orthonormality of $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}$ and because the stationary distribution ϕ_0 is given by $\phi_0(z) = \frac{d(z)}{\text{tr}(D)}$. This explains why we included the prefactor $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{tr}(D)}}$ in equation 2.9.

This finally gives us

$$D_t^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_{j=1}^{N-1} (\psi_j(\mathbf{x}) - \psi_j(\mathbf{y}))^2 \lambda_j^{2t}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

the desired claim in equation 2.15

A.2 Included Variables of the V-Dem dataset

Table A.1: The 25 variables from the V-Dem dataset that are included.

	Tag	Indicator/index name from [68]
Indices		
	v2x_suffr	Share of population with suffrage
	v2x_elecoff	Elected officials index
Indicators		
Free expression	v2mecenefm	Government censorship effort – Media
	v2meharjn	Harassment of journalists
	v2meslfcen	Media self-censorship
	v2mebias	Media bias
	v2merange	Print/broadcast media perspectives
	v2mecrit	Print/broadcast media critical
	v2cldiscm	Freedom of discussion for men
	v2cldiscw	Freedom of discussion for women
	v2clacfree	Freedom of academic and cultural expression
Free association	v2psparban	Party ban
	v2psbars	Barriers to parties
	v2psoppaut	Opposition parties autonomy
	v2elmulpar	Elections multiparty
	v2cseeorgs	CSO [civil society organizations] entry and exit
	v2csreprss	CSO repression
Clean elections	v2eembaut	EMB [election management body] autonomy
	v2eembcap	EMB capacity
	v2elrgstry	Election voter registry
	v2elvotbuy	Election vote buying
	v2elirreg	Election other voting irregularities
	v2elintim	Election government intimidation
	v2elpeace	Election other electoral violence
	v2elfrfair	Election free and fair

A.3 Hyperparameters Used for the Training of the Decoders

Table A.2: Hyperparameters used for the diffusion map of the Swiss roll

Hidden layers	(50, 50, 50, 50)
Training size	2500
Number of epochs	50
Batch size	32
β	1e-06
initial learning rate	0.05
learning rate schedule	Stepwise reduction
step size	10
reduction factor	0.5

Table A.3: Hyperparameters used for the diffusion map of the Ising dataset

Hidden layers	(50, 150)
Training size	11008
Number of epochs	100
Batch size	32
β	1e-06
initial learning rate	0.01
learning rate schedule	Reduce on plateau
threshold	0.01
reduction factor	0.1

Table A.4: Hyperparameters used for the diffusion map and PCA of the FPUT system dataset

Hidden layers	(50, 50)
Training size	11000
Number of epochs	200
Batch size	32
β	1e-06
initial learning rate	0.01
learning rate schedule	Reduce on plateau
threshold	0.01
reduction factor	0.5

Table A.5: Hyperparameters used for the diffusion map and PCA of the V-Dem dataset

Hidden layers	(130, 130, 130)
Training size	11296
Number of epochs	100
Batch size	50
β	1e-06
initial learning rate	0.01
learning rate schedule	Reduce on plateau
threshold	0.01
reduction factor	0.1

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Erklärung

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich diese Arbeit selbstständig ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter und ohne Verwendung anderer als der angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel verfasst habe. Ich habe keine generativen KI-Anwendungen verwendet, um Texte oder Abbildungen in dieser Arbeit zu generieren.

Darüber hinaus versichere ich, dass die elektronische Version der Arbeit mit der gedruckten Version übereinstimmt.

Leipzig, den 6. November 2025

Friedrich Pagenkopf